

Crossing The Boundaries of The Archaeology of Somapura Mahavihara: Alternative Approaches and Propositions

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Abstract

As it is overtly recognizable in the archaeological scholarship in South Asia, the historical and archaeological narratives regarding Somapura Mahavihara of Bangladesh are represented by a distinct brand of monument-centrism. The narratives produced at a huge scale from these perspectives have established stereotyped and reductionist notions of the mahavihara and Buddhist samgha. In this paper, we attempt to cross the boundaries of the knowledge of this monument-centrism and dominant text based elaborations on Buddhism by incorporating the methods of survey archaeology, excavation, geoarchaeological investigations and epigraphic enumerations. What we have found out is with profound consequences. For example, the mahavihara remains were core of a settlement and was within a network of settlements in early medieval Varendri. Consistent changes in the alluvial landscape settings had significant impact on the lifeways of the settlements. We have proposed provisional stratigraphy of recent excavations which suggest that Buddhist samgha, probably, had to negotiate with the continuous shifts of the channels and regular floods. At the same time, the nature and functioning of these establishments, we have interpreted, were, conditioned, directly or indirectly, by the agrarian expansion and its complex articulations in Varendri during seventh-eighth century and onwards.

...Scholars of Indian Buddhism have taken canonical monastic rules and formal literary descriptions of the monastic ideal preserved in very late manuscripts and treated them as if they were accurate reflections of the religious life and career of actual practicing Buddhist monks in early India. Such a procedure has, of course, placed archaeology and epigraphy in a very awkward position. If, then, archaeology and epigraphy are to be in the service of a "history" based on written sources of this kind, then they are going to have to "support and amplify" something that very probably did not exist: they going to have to sit quietly in the corner spinning cloth for the emperor's new clothes (Schopen 1991: 5-6).

Buddhist research is dominated by textually-based scholars, or by historians of art or architecture, relegating archaeologists to a solitary role of primary producer, not venturing further than the description of excavated remains (Coningham 1998: 122).

THE HISTORICITY OF THE ARCHAEOLOGY OF SOMAPURA MAHAVIHARA

The structural remains enlisted as one of the world heritage sites in Bangladesh, and widely recognized as Somapura Mahavihara (Plate 1, 2, 3) built by the Pala king Dharmapala in around eighth century CE, have been under the scholastic gaze for a very long time. After coming to light through surveys during the colonial period (see Cunningham 1882; Westmacott 1875), the excavations on the site have revealed the monumental remains that were considered, before the recognition of Vikramshila Mahavihara through excavations at Antichak, Bihar, as the largest single-unit Buddhist 'monastery' in the Indian sub-continent. In spite of the fact that excavations have been carried out in colonial, Pakistan and post-independence Bangladesh periods, the report by Dikshit (1938) has remained as the most comprehensive one to date. The architectural remains consisting mainly of a quadrangular vihara and a central shrine decorated with terracotta plaques and stone sculptures also include several other subsidiary structures within the courtyard and outside the main vihara. Although these monumental remains have been addressed by and engaged in innumerable scholastic researches, these enterprises have predominantly taken architectural and art historical perspectives - even if we consider the

vulnerability of such disciplinary categories, as their boundaries are often blurred - as their central frame of reference. This is a hegemonic trend in the studies of South Asian Buddhism as has been spelled out by Schopen (1991) and Coningham (1998) (see also, Coningham 2001). The publications on sculptural, architectural and iconographic aspects are quite significant in number, and many of the foundational publications on ancient Indian art and architecture have attended to the monumental remains of Somapura Mahavihara - presently located at Paharpur of Badalgachhi Upazila, Narogaon District - with deserved importance (see for example, Asher 1980; Chakrabarti 2003; Gail 1999; Sandy and Ahmed 1986; Weiner 1962; Huntington 1985; Mevissen 2006; Alam 1985; Saraswati 1962). They have also been central to scholastic and heritage-related policy-making enterprises, especially since their inclusion as a world heritage site by UNESCO (see, for example, several papers in Alam 2004a). It must be acknowledged that these works have contributed immensely towards the understanding of these monuments, stone sculptures, terracotta plaques on the central shrine, etc., from different theoretical and methodological perspectives. We must point to the fact that many of these scholastic productions, however, have been dominantly monument-centric.

The monument-centrism we are identifying in the case of Somapura Mahavihara is not, historically and theoretically, an isolated position. Partly these approaches adhere to the colonial legacy of the formation of the discipline, where an understanding of Indian Buddhism has been connected with various protestant presuppositions and traditions of Judeo-Christianity (Schopen 1991) and different structures and processes of unequal colonial encounter. On the other hand, as Smith has shown, the monument-centrism is embodied in the ideas and concept of cultural heritage that has its genealogy in Europe. Smith contended:

The use of the term monument is particularly important in the European context. As Choay (2001) documents, the word took on particular registers of power, greatness, and beauty during the seventeenth century and came to affirm a sense of grand public schemes and aesthetic sensibilities. The monument became 'a witness to history and a work of art' that took on a commemorative role in triggering certain public memories and values, and is a concept that has come to embody a particular European vision of the world (Choay 2001: 15; Carrier 2005). The French idea of *patrimoine* – specifically the concept of inheritance – also underwrites the aesthetic grandness (Choay 2001). This sense of inheritance promotes the idea that the present has a particular 'duty' to the past and its monuments. The duty of the present is to receive and revere what has been passed on and in turn pass this inheritance, untouched, to future generations (2006: 19).

Smith then showed in brief how the ideals and practices of perceiving and addressing monuments in these ways become naturalized for non-western contexts as hegemonic global 'common sense' (Smith 2006: 19-21). The interrelated discourses of archaeology and cultural heritage, besides, have essentialized monument-centrism as it allows for the invocation of a glorious and tolerant national identity through, as Sen (2002: 352) argues, the representation of a monumental ancestry. Without going into more details of the genealogy of particular reductionist trends of archaeological practice that have been normalized for Somapura Mahavihara, we would like to assert that various strands and nuances of the past settlements associated with the vihara could be unpacked by going beyond the monument-centrism.

GOING BEYOND MONUMENT-CENTRISM: OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

In this paper, we would like to make an attempt to understand the history of Somapura Mahavihara in relation to its hinterland zone and to the landscape context in which it is situated (Fig 1). A few works in recent times have tried to address the Buddhist religious establishments in the Indian sub-continent from different perspectives (e.g., Shaw 2013). Our primary objective, in this situation, is to try to

see whether it is possible to debunk the established history of the vihara by going beyond the normalized and institutionalized paradigms. In this effort, we use available interpretations and evidences from published materials, as well as data collected from our fieldwork. We incorporate and correlate data from archaeological surveying, excavations, epigraphic sources and geoarchaeological investigations.

It has been presumed that Somapura Mahavihara is a single-unit 'monastery'. We have conducted surveying in an area of approximately one square kilometer around the present monumental remains. The recent archaeological works in northwestern Bangladesh, in the southern part of present Dinajpur District in particular, have hypothesized that many of the monumental remains are part, or even core, of the early medieval settlements in the sub-region that was known, at least after the ninth century CE, as Varendri (see, Sen 2012). A recently deciphered inscription of the time of Dharmapala (Furui 2011) referring to a donation of land plots, to Buddhist *samghas* of three facilities including a *viharika* and a *gandhakuti* (perfume chamber), established by a subordinate ruler and his consort at Somapura Mahavihara supports our postulation that the mahavihara not only constituted the several structures that are exposed and visible now, but also had other associated structures and habitation nearby. Through our surveying, albeit incomplete with regard to the coverage and resolution, we attempt to recognize the archaeological and geoarchaeological variables that can make substantial contributions to our understanding of the history of the mahavihara establishment and other structural and habitational remains as composition of several settlements or as a distinct settlement.

Data from recent exploratory excavations (2007-08 and 2008-09) within the courtyard, presented in the paper by Alam and Sultana (2013), are crucial for our interpretations. The excavations were conducted in a very limited area in comparison to the entire area of the courtyard, and the horizontal exposure of the deposits could have been more significant in terms of building a more accurate and reliable stratigraphy. The excavations, nevertheless, have supplied us with very important data regarding the vertical association of various deposits. It must be noted that the data presented by Alam and Sultana (2013) has not been interpreted and presented within a systematic stratigraphic framework. One of our crucial objectives was to correlate the data, despite its limited quality, to propose a provisional stratigraphic sequence, as the physical relationship of the deposits in various trenches could not be established on actual ground. In our surveying, we also continued the enterprise of understanding the landscape context undertaken by Rahman (2005) through recording and analysis of outcrops and accidental sedimentary sections and by documenting geomorphological features. Data recorded by handheld GPS receivers was used to map the

archaeological occurrences and geomorphological features. The data was then used to understand the landscape in Google Earth and different bands of Landsat™ (bands 1, 2, 3 and 7 in particular) imageries to establish a tentative outline of the settlement zone and to map present

geomorphological variables on the regional scale by digitization and conversion procedures. ArcMap 10 was used to correlate the digitized data and for the preparation of maps for the analysis of landscapes.

Fig. 1: Monumental remains of the Somapura Mahavihara in the present geomorphic context

SURVEYING FOR A SETTLEMENT ZONE

We have conducted archaeological surveying to recognize the signatures of occupation or human activity in the vicinity of the present mahavihara establishment, in spite of the fact that a considerable proportion of the remaining traces of any activity might easily be buried under the alluvium or could be eroded away by the transforming processes of the alluvial landscape. We looked for even the flimsiest traces of past human activity, both in its primary and secondary contexts.

We conducted intensive surveying within an area of 1 square kilometer around the presently exposed remains of the mahavihara. Four particular occurrences of brick-built structural activities were recognized and recorded, excluding Goal Bhita, and a surface scatter of potsherds, both in their primary and secondary contexts, was found. The brief contextual characteristics of Goal Bhita and the occurrences are as follows:

Fig. 2: Locations of occurrences, core settlement zone (shown in solid line) and hypothetically extended settlement zone (shown in broken line)

The Goal Bhitia (Figs 2-3): This is a present village on the northeast corner of the mahavihara. The village is irregular in shape and it measures 195meters from north to south and 182meters from east to west. The habitational area of the village occupies the higher part of the landscape. Surface scatters of potsherds and brick-bats are sporadically visible because of the predominant anthropogenic activities (Plates 4-6). On a few accidental sections, exposed by the digging of the local people, deposits of potsherds and brick-bats are noticeable.

Dikshit (1929: 61) identified this place as the Vat-ghohali, where the vihara of the arhats was located – according to the Paharpur Copper Plate Inscription of the time of Buddagupta (G. E. 159, c. 479 CE) - and the land was donated to the vihara. The entire village, we think, is a settlement or part of a settlement associated with the currently exposed monumental remains, with both structural and habitational deposits. Along with the old tanks, it is possible to draw a fuzzy boundary of the settlement that is semi-circular in shape.

A mound is visible in a portion of the village, as there is no overlying present habitation (Plate 7). It is a large, low

structural mound, just on the northeast corner of the present remains of the mahavihara. The mound measures 108meters from east to west and 60meters from north to south. A section on the mound (Fig. 4; Plate 8) indicates that the deposits at the upper part of the mound are filling possibly from a later (post-excavation?) period. The lower part of the deposits contains regular masonry work (brick-built walls?).

The visibility of the records is fair to good, varying according to seasonal variations, associated vegetation growth (or decrease) and anthropogenic modifications. Obtrusiveness is poor to fair because of the anthropogenic modifications and relocations of the cultural materials. Accessibility is very poor in the case of surmounting modern habitations and good in the case of smaller open areas.

Occurrences of regular brick-built masonries and potsherds: We have detected four occurrences of regular brick-built structures, partially preserved, and exposed because of digging by local people. The spatial contexts of these occurrences are very close to each other. They are confined within the areas in between two beels (low lands with swampy condition and seasonally flooded during the monsoon) locally called as Kholisagari Beel and Gazaria Beel, respectively. Both of these beels are situated 600 meters to the north of the

Fig. 3: Spatial distribution of Goal Bhitia and occurrences (modified after the image from Google Earth)

monumental remains of the mahavihara. Kholisagari Beel is to the west of Gazaria Beel and they are located 300 meters and Gazaria Beel is just to the east of Goal Bhitia. Occurrences 1, 2 and 4 are flimsy remains of regular brick-built masonries (Plate 9-14) and they were constructed on the sandy alluvium of the floodplain named by the Water Resources Planning Organization's (WARPO) digitized data

as Teesta Meander Floodplain. Occurrence 3 is high density potsherds (>50 pieces/sq. meter), and the spatial extent of the occurrence spreads downslope towards the Kholishagari Beel (Plates 15-16). Curiously, low density deposits of potsherds (<50 pieces/sq. meter) are detectable within the sediments at the bottom of the beels. The density suggests that these potsherds were not spatially relocated. Rather they were exposed, we suppose, because of the erosional processes at the bottom of the beels (see, Fig 2 for geomorphological contexts of the occurrences).

Fig. 4: Section on Goal Bhita showing deposits and regular brick-built masonries¹

The visibility of the brick-built masonry remains is low to moderate because of the sediment and vegetation cover. Obtrusiveness is high to moderate because of the very nature of the remains. On the other hand, the visibility of potsherds on the higher surface is fair. The visibility of the potsherds on the bed, however, is very poor because of the colour of the sediments. Obtrusiveness is moderate to high, as most of the potsherds have a contrasting colour with regard to the sediments. These occurrences indicate that, spatially, they were part of a single habitation zone, not very far away from the present remains of the mahavihara.

Occurrences of potsherds are detectable to the south of the present monumental remains of the mahavihara. Due to the sporadic occurrences and low density, and low intensity and coverage, they have not been separately plotted on the map. At the same time, boundary of a tentative core settlement

zone of the mahavihara could be outlined (Fig. 2), considering the spatial distribution of the potsherds that are on the surface and on the accidental sections. On the basis of the reference to an archaeological place – Sonarpara Bhita – located 3.5 km to the east of Paharpur by Hossain (2004: 47), the zone has been hypothetically extended (Fig. 2). Consideration of the channel courses and topography of the floodplain in relation to the occurrences of cultural materials, moreover, was a factor for delineating the boundary. The nature and locations of archaeological deposits in the extended zone must be tested on the basis of future surveys. Otherwise, different locations of archaeological places may well represent different settlement areas with considerably large spatial boundaries.

THE EXPLORATORY EXCAVATIONS AND PROPOSITION OF A PROVISIONAL STRATIGRAPHY

Exploratory trenches were taken in different periods on various locations of the courtyard and on the wings after the independence of Bangladesh, though reports of the excavations have not been systematically published². Alam and Sultana (2013) have published a preliminary report of four exploratory trenches that were taken by the Department of Archaeology, Ministry of Cultural Affairs, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, in the seasons of 2007-08 and 2008-09. One of these was dug in the 2007-08 season in the northeast corner of the central temple on the pradakshinapatha (circumambulatory passage) (PAH.3). During the season of 2008-09, three trenches were taken, of which section drawings and descriptions of the stratification of two are published in Alam and Sultana (2013). One trench was taken on the northeast corner of the central temple just outside the enclosure wall of the pradakshinapatha (PAH. 2) (Plates 17, 18). Another trench was dug at the southwest corner of the central temple within the courtyard (PAH. 1) (Plates 19). The third trench was dug to the north of the main entrance of the centre temple (PAH. 4), of which a few descriptions are available in Alam and Sultana (2013) (Plate 20; see, Fig 5 for the locations of the trenches). From the published description of the stratification and drawings of the sections, and through our understanding of the deposits during our presence in excavations of 2008-09, we have tried to establish a stratigraphic sequence of different periods of the central temple and the mahavihara (see, Table 1 and Fig. 6 for section correlation, and stratigraphic succession) for the first time. It must be acknowledged that owing to the absence of horizontal exposures of deposits on a larger extent compared to the area of the courtyard, the stratigraphy that is proposed below (Table 1) is tentative. Further excavations with more horizontal exposures to establish stratigraphic relations between the temple and the wings of the mahavihara may verify, confirm and elaborate the stratigraphy in the future.

Natural soil: The natural surface of the landform on which the first settlement was constructed was not soil if it is defined according to sedimentology. Medium to coarse light grey sands with <20% silt mark these sediments (layer 21 of PAH.2 and layer 10 of PAH.1). The first occupation on this location was on floodplain silty sand with massive structure. There is no sign of pedogenesis in this particular layer in any of the trenches. The layer occupies 14.30 to 15.50m above the mean sea level, and 3.5m – 4.75m below the present habitational surface of the area, and the surface of

the courtyard of the vihara. A prudent interpretation of the contemporary landscape indicates the flood-prone nature of the occupation above this surface. It could also be inferred that the earlier evidences of habitations and their destructions and modifications have been buried under 3.5-4 meters of predominantly flood-born floodplain sediments on the space that was occupied later by present structural assemblages of the mahavihara and associated structures and habitation deposits. The location might occupy the top of a palaeo-levee.

Fig. 5: Ground plan of the mahavihara remains with locations of trenches (modified after Dikshit 1938)

Level I: Pre-structural period 1(Plates 21-23): The traces of the first habitation on this location suggest that they were probably characterized by an occupation without the use of brick as a construction material. This period is represented on PAH. 1 by a small and shallow pit (4cm-6cm in depth)

[layer 9] in floodplain sediments filled with charcoal, ash and potsherds consisting mostly of bases of bowls of red ware. On PAH. 2, this period is represented by a 20cm thick deposit (layer 20) constituting dark grey clayey soil mixed with very well sorted frequent potsherds, ranging from 3cm-

5cm in length. Most of the potsherds are in parallel position with regard to the surface. The formation processes of this particular deposit are not evident. Although Alam and Sultana (2013) think that this deposit was formed under a swampy environment within a stagnant waterlogged condition on the basis of interpreted depositional environment of the dark grey clayey sedimentary matrix, the sorting, frequency and orientation of the potsherds indicate that they are in situ, and it is probable that this deposit was anthropogenic in origin. The potsherds within the sticky and clayey sediments were rammed, and in this way, this deposit might suggest a construction phase to provide an activity surface of the occupants. It seems that the deposit sloped downward from PAH.1 to PAH.2, and activity surfaces and occupational debris of this particular period were spatially heterogeneous. The deposit of PAH.1 – representing the activity zone -was confined within the area of the PAH.2 beneath the present central shrine, and the pit or rubbish disposal area was on its edge towards the southeast. The first occupants of the area inhabited on the surface of an active floodplain 15.50m-14.25m above the mean sea level, and the surface was sloping towards the north.

Table 1: Correlation among deposits and masonries of the sections and provisional stratigraphy

PAH. 1	PAH. 2	PAH. 3	Provisional Stratigraphy
1	1	1	Level IX: Structural Period 4
2	2	2	
3	4	3	Level VIII: Structural Period 3, Phase 2 ???
	5	3	Level VII: Flood (?)
4	6	4	Level VI: Structural Period 3, Phase 1
	7	5	
	8	6	Level V: Structural Period 2
	9	7	
	10	8	
	11	9	
5	12	9	Level IV: Flood 2
6	13		Level III: Structural Period 1(?)
	14		
	15		
	16		
	17		
	18		
7	19		Level II: Flood 1
8	20		Level I: Pre-Structural Period 1
9	21		Natural Soil
10			

Fig. 6: Correlation of sections with regard to altitudes

Level II: Flood 1(Plate 23): Deposits of the first settlement were found to be buried under a deposit of fine-medium sand with >10% silt. In PAH.2, the sandy deposit is 22cm

thick (layer 19) and in PAH.1 the deposit (layer 8) is 25cm thick. The entire sandy unit is massive, and there are no visible traces of bedding. This deposit probably represents a

low to medium energy overbank flood born facies. The deposit is at 14.60 m – 14.82m above the present mean sea level in PAH.2, and at 15.50 – 16.00m above the mean sea level in PAH. 1. The altitudinal difference suggests that the flood deposit overlaid the original relief of the earlier surface that slopes towards the north. This flood, possibly representing one event, might have destroyed the earliest habitations and buried the remains.

Level III: Structural Period 1(?) (Plates 23-25): This second period of occupation of the area started upon the surface formed by the earlier flood. Deposits of very dark grey clayey sediment with frequently occurred (>70%), homogenous and very well sorted potsherds with 15cm – 16cm (layer 18; PAH.2) and 22cm – 30cm (layer 7; PAH. 1) thickness represents this period. This deposit was probably a rammed floor made over a considerably large area for occupational purposes, the nature of which is unknown. The occurrence of ring stands in a huge proportion within the sediments of the later period, possibly representing another flood event, indicates that unknown occupational activities of a considerable nature took place in this period.

Occurrence of a few brick-fragments within the matrix of potsherds might well hint at some kind of activity pertaining to construction of a brick-built structure. The categorization of this period as structural is, therefore, very tentative and provisional. The layers (17 – 13, PAH. 2) representing various deposits related to the construction, modification and destruction of the occupations of this period hint at structural activities. For example, layer 17 reflects occupational activity (dark grey clayey sediments with potsherds and brick fragments), and layer 16-14 represent the occupational deposits of various compositions and frequency of potsherds, brick pieces, etc. Layer 13 possesses ash and charcoal with very frequent and comparatively large potsherds. It seems that the occurrence of charcoal and ash is a kind of occupational rubbish, rather than the signature of abandonment and destruction. These deposits are absent in PAH. 1, indicating that the main activity zone of the period was located in the area where PAH. 2 was taken, that is, in the vicinity of the central shrine of the later mahavihara.

Fig. 7: Plan of structural remains with associated floor underneath the central temple. The section was taken in A-B location. (Plan courtesy:Alam and Sultana 2013)

Level IV: Flood 2(Plate 26): This second event of flood is recognizable through a deposit in trench PAH. 1. This deposit constitutes medium to fine sand and complete ring stands, numerous in number (Plate 27). From a 30cm – 40

cm thick sandy deposit in a 1 sq. m. area, more than 15 ring stands were recovered in PAH. 1. As a particular type of pottery, ring stands (Plates 28) are common from different archaeological sites from different time spans. These ring stands were found to be clustered in a haphazard way

without any particular organization or orientation. It seems that they had been dumped before they were buried by the sediments from an episodic flood. As the sand of this deposit is homogenous, massive and laid on the surface of the previous occupational deposit, it might possibly not be originated from anthropogenic activity. The deposit is identifiable in PAH. 3 (layer 9), on which the first detectable and distinctive structural activity took place. Although this deposit is not recognizable in PAH. 2, it is probable that the first structural occupation of the locale was destroyed and buried by a major flood event of a considerable intensity and strength. The reason for the absence of such deposit in PAH. 2 is probably later constructions which destroyed the earlier signatures. The slope of the deposit is towards the west.

Level V: Structural period 2 (Plates 29-33): During the excavation in 2007-08, a portion of a cell of a brick-built structure was partially exposed along with associated floor (layer 8 of PAH. 3) (fig. 7). The walls were found to be running beneath the present central shrine of the mahavihara. Alam (2004b) has also reported this pre-central shrine structure. It would be relevant to note that van Lohuizen-de Leeuw (1985) has referred to the pre-monastic structures in earlier excavations. The central shrine was constructed over the remains of this earlier brick-built structure.

Alam and Sultana (2013) referred to a few other walls which, according to them, were associated with this structure. In another trench (PAH.4) in front of the staircases to the north of the central shrine, dug in 2008-09, they have identified two parallel walls, which they think are connected to this structure. Although their description is very non-specific in the published paper, from our observation during the excavation and from the published photographs, the presence of these parallel walls is evident. Alam and Sultana also described these walls in the following way:

Another brick paved floor (16) was partially exposed at the depth of 1.08m from the floor (11) and (12) for entering the central shrine lying at the height of 17.16m from the mean sea level. The floor was constructed by paving two courses of bricks, measuring 30cm × 30 cm × 4 cm. ... The parallel walls were built by cutting the floor (16). The parallel walls and the floors are not contemporary. These two architectural features, therefore, are not contemporary (translation by the authors)(2013: 12).

From the description above, the stratigraphic association of the floor is not distinctive, though the parallel walls were associated, according to the narration in the same paper, with the portion of the cell and floor of the pre-shrine brick-built structure. The floor, therefore, must predate the walls, possibly belonging to earlier construction phase of the same structure. We have not included this particular phase in our

proposed provisional stratigraphy, as its nature and position in reference to other walls and deposits is not clear, at least in the representation of the recording in the paper.

These particular pre-central shrine brick-built structures, and an earlier level of the monastic cells, have given rise to interesting debates regarding their nature and function. Alam (2004b: 53-4) has identified this structure as the Jain vihara that has been referred to in the copper plate inscription Paharpur from the time of Budhagupta (c. 479 CE), and he dated the structure, quite uncritically, to the 'Gupta' period. On the other hand, Alam and Sultana (2013) think that these structural components were part of a Brahmanical temple with cellular construction and that the stone sculptures - the date, provenance and styles of which have stirred a long-lasting debate among scholars (see Lefèvre 2012 for a summary of the debate and Asher 1980) – were possibly collected from this earlier edifice. The location of the Jain vihara referred to in the copper plate inscription has not yet been determined, and even the primary provenance of the inscription that was recovered from the excavation of this site in 1927 has not yet been proved with any degree of certainty. Scholars like Asher (1980:15) have put forward an alternative interpretation of the phrase 'Buddhist' that has been earlier inferred to denote 'Jain'. He also points to the fact that no Jain or Buddhist remains dating to fifth century CE have been identified at or in the vicinity of Paharpur. On the contrary, Furui has suggested that,

The existence of the plate does not prove the presence of a Jain or other establishment at the present Paharpur, as a copper plate can be moved. I assume that the plate came to the mahavihara in a later period, when the samgha acquired rights over the land donated in the copper plate. We cannot know the exact location of the original establishment but can be sure it was in the Rajshahi-Naogaon area, as Dakshinanshaka-vithi is mentioned in the Jagadishpur plate³ also. (personal communication)

Wherever the location of the Jain vihara might be, it could be asserted that the structural remains underlying the present central shrine cannot be the Jain vihara as far as chronology is concerned. Simultaneously, the cellular nature of this pre-shrine structure cannot be determined through a structure that is partially exposed.

Lefèvre(2012), by thoroughly dealing with the earlier arguments on the provenance of the stone sculptures, contended that the sculptures were not external and were basically part of an original iconographic scheme that, in his opinion, differed from those proposed by Asher (1980) and Gail (1999).

van Lohuizen-de Leeuw (1985: 748) has pointed to this pre-central shrine structure and, by refuting Dikhsit's argument in favour of a 'Jain Monastery'. She opined that the earlier structure could be a Buddhist one. We have to

remember that in the most elaborate excavation report to date, Dikshit (1938: 20-24) talked about various construction periods and levels of the monastery and the central shrine. His descriptions of different periods are very non-specific, and they cannot be related stratigraphically to each other in absence of textual and graphic presentation, and interpretation of stratigraphy. But in these excavations, van Lohuizen-de Leeuw (1985) contended, it was possible to verify the three periods of occupation referred to by Dikshit.

In the report of the excavation campaign of the early 1980s⁴, van Lohuizen-de Leeuw (1985: 744-45) and Alam (2004b: 52-3) referred to an earlier structural level that was identified within a confined area of the monastic cells under the period I described by Dikshit (1938). The stratigraphic relationships between this earliest level and the pre-central shrine level, or the levels of the central shrine, have not been demonstrated.

We are not interested to go into the details here of these debates on the style, iconography, chronology and provenance of the stone sculptures, or about the nature of earlier structures of this period. It is evident, however, that there was an imposing brick-built structure, the walls of which measured 2 meters in width at floor level, before the construction of the present central shrine. More horizontal excavation around the present central shrine and reliable chronometric dating from samples may shed some light on the nature, function and date of this structural assemblage. The earlier structural level that was detected through the excavations in the early 80s beneath the monastic cells, as van Lohuizen-de Leeuw (1985) noted, could be contemporary to the structure we are talking about in this level. The stratigraphic relation between these two must be established by further studies. It could be postulated, on the basis of typological dating of the potsherds from the earlier levels of the excavation we are talking about, that the date of this structure cannot be fifth century CE. The idea of a 'Gupta period' Buddhist or Jain monastery could be firmly rejected on the basis of this stratigraphy. We would like to propose a much later date in the late seventh or early eighth century for this pre-central shrine structure on the basis of pottery from earlier levels.

It is also not improbable that Dharmapala built this monastery upon the ruins of, or by destroying, the earlier structure, the nature of which is unknown at this moment. On the other hand, Tibetan tradition, recorded by both Taranatha and Sumpa (Dutt 1962: 374; Chimpa and Chattopadhyaya 1970: 265-66), refers to the building of this mahavihara by Devapala (c. 810 – 850 CE), son of Dharmapala. Dutt (1962) has not rejected this possibility. He thinks that although the name of Devapala occurs nowhere in the Paharpur ruins, identification of this vihara in several clay seals recovered from the excavation as 'Dharmapala Mahavihara'⁵ could be 'meant to be commemorative – the son's dutiful tribute to the memory of

the father' (Dutt 1962: 274-5). It is, therefore, not unquestionably established that Dharmapala established the mahavihara, although the accuracy and authenticity of the account of Taranatha is questionable (Majumder 1943: 182-87). The question about whether the mahavihara was built by Dharmapala or Devapala is not very crucial for our understanding. We are more interested to know why the mahavihara was built upon the earlier remains in a dynamic and continuously changing alluvial landscape. We will come to this point later when we take into account the enigma of the entire establishment and settlement in terms of contemporary alluvial landscape.

Level VI: Earliest period of central shrine and mahavihara(Plate 33): We are proposing this period assuming that the wings with the cells of the mahavihara are contemporaneous to the central shrine. This level is marked by a rammed floor below the level at which the stone sculptures are located. This floor could possibly be attributed to the earliest level of the present central shrine, and probably to the earliest level of the present mahavihara complex. Layer 8 of PAH. 2 and layer 4 of PAH. 3 correspond to the activity surface comprising a rammed floor of small to very small brick bats and powdered bricks measuring 6cm-8cm in thickness. The later occupational deposits are not clearly recognizable in these two trenches, possibly owing to the later reuse and modification of deposits of this world heritage monument for conservation purposes.

Although van Lohuizen-de Leeuw narrated that Dikshit had identified four levels, or periods, in the central shrine, a careful reading the excavation report suggests that she might have misunderstood Dikshit's elaborations. Dikshit clearly referred to different construction periods above the second terrace of the main/central temple. In his words, 'the structures on the second terrace illustrate clearly the different periods at which the main temple underwent reconstruction or repair' (Dikshit 1938: 13). He then goes on to a descriptive representation of different construction periods above the second terrace of the central temple, referring to four altogether (Dikshit 1938: 13-15). We must note that Dikshit has not elaborated on different construction and occupational periods and phases in relation to the first terrace, except a few imprecise references to a few structures which are later or earlier, and, moreover, he did not make any observations on their stratigraphic relationship.

One of the most interesting pieces of evidence was found overlying the floor of this period. In the trench of PAH. 3, a layer (8cm-10cm) of dark grey ash and charcoal was found overlying the section facing the south and the east (Plate 33). This layer of ash and charcoal provides evidence in support of a burning activity during or after this period. A broken bronze statue of Buddha (Plate 48) found during the excavation in the early 80s in one of the monastic cells bears the marks of burning. Presently displayed in the Paharpur

site museum, the statue has greyish carbon coating on the surface and bulging marks along with cracks, and these signatures attest to the fact that this sculptural piece was heated after its construction (Pranab Chattopaddhaya, personal communication). The date of the burning event cannot be determined, as there are no published reports with stratigraphic details on the excavations.

For indirect support, we may refer to Dikshit's version of the report on monastic cells. He describes that:

Turning to the actual monastery building, attention may be drawn to the cells situated immediately to the east of the outer hall of the gateway, which must have been one of the most important places in the monastery area, and was probably used as an office or strong room by the head or elder of the mahavihara.... Big lumps of charcoal were recovered in this room, which from the grain, appear to be the remains of palm-wood and indicate the use of rafters of this material for the roofing and their destruction by fire. In this connection, it is interesting to find in a Nalanda inscription that the forces of Vangala (i.e. East Bengal) once attacked and set fire to the monastery of Somapura (Dikshit 1938: 20).

Besides, Dikshit referred to scattered charcoal pieces from room 133, and he suggested that 'these were the charred remains of the rafters employed in the roof' (1938: 34). Heaps of charcoal and ashes in the dining hall have also been interpreted by him as the evidence of destruction by some conflagration (Dikshit 1938: 29).

The epigraphic reference to the burning of Somapura Mahavihara and the death of Karunasrimitra in that attack (Sastri 1999: 103-105) could provide a clue to these deposits of ash and charcoal in both monastic cells and floor of central temple. To establish the correspondence between the event referred to in the Stone Inscription of Vipulasrimitra and the event interpreted through archaeological evidence, it is necessary, first, to establish contemporaneity of these deposits in two locations through stratigraphic correlation; and secondly, to get a firm understanding about the chronological corroboration between the event described in epigraphic sources and the event inferred from archaeological deposit.

Sircar (1942) dated the inscription on palaeographic ground to c. twelfth century CE, and Ray (1387 BS: 523) thinks that the inscription was issued at the end of eleventh century CE or in the first half of the twelfth century CE. On the other hand, following Majumder (1931-32: 97-101), Dutt (1962: 376) postulates that the date of the inscription could be assigned to first half of the twelfth century CE. He thinks that the event of setting fire to the monastery could be placed to about hundred years before the inscriptional record, that is, around the middle of the eleventh century CE. Dutt speculates on the event in the following way:

At that time a family migrating perhaps from the south, with the surname Varman, had set up a sort of kingdom

in East Bengal (Vangal). The first king was named Jatavarma. He seems to have been inimical to Buddhism and tried to achieve notoriety by destroying the great monastery that was flourishing at Somapura in his time in northern Bengal. With this object, he sent troops who marched on the Dharmapala Monastery and set fire to it (1962: 376).

Ray (1387 BS: 419) also relates this event to Jatavarma's antagonistic attitude towards Buddhism. Without referring to such speculative correlation between epigraphic and historical narrative, which is based mainly upon the speculated non-patronizing and antagonistic attitudes of Varman rulers towards Buddhism as a whole, it could be claimed that the evidence of charcoal and ash provides firm support for an event of burning in the mahavihara. It is also evident that the deposit of charcoal and ash on the earliest floor of the main temple, nevertheless, cannot chronologically be the event of burning referred to in the stone inscription of Vipulasrimitra.

The floor most probably belongs to later part of the eighth century or the earlier part of the ninth century CE, if we accept that the temple was built simultaneously with present monastic establishments. The event of burning, then, must have taken place at that time or afterward. But the event cannot be chronologically placed to such a late date as the eleventh century CE, considering the various periods of constructions and reconstructions of the main temple already referred to by Dikshit. The reconstruction activities have also been hinted at in the stone inscription of Vipulasrimitra, in which it says that the monk Vipulasrimitra had built a Tara Temple at Somapura Mahavihara and patronized a good deal of masonry work in Somapura Mahavihara (Sastri 1999: 104; Majumder 1931-32), possibly as restoration and reconstruction after the second event of burning. The lumps of charcoal and ash in the monastic cell recovered by Dikshit could be related to either of these two events of burning – one attested by stratigraphic evidence and another by epigraphic sources.

At the same time, Ray (1387BS: 388) pointed to the fact that Pratihara King Mahendrapala extended his kingdom upto Paharpur during the reign of Narayanpala (c. 861-917 CE). Dikshit (1938: 5) refers to the invasion of Pala kingdom by Gurjara(?) emperor Bhoja I and Mahendrapala in the last quarter of ninth century. One pillar inscription bearing the name of Mahendrapala discovered from the excavation of Paharpur has been cited as evidence. The evidence can be falsified on the basis of discovery of the Jagjivanpur copper plate inscription of Mahendrapala (Bhattacharya 2005-2006; Bhattacharya 1992 and 2000), and through this inscription a new Pala ruler was identified bearing the name of Mahendrapala. Mahendrapala of the stone pillar inscription of Paharpur, more probably, was this Pala ruler Mahendrapala. There is no possibility of imagining an attack or a donation from the Pratihara king at any moment of the occupational period of Somapura Mahavihara. The deposit of charcoal and ash, therefore, cannot be associated with this event.

Level VII: Flood (?): This level is highly propositional as it is only attested by a deposit (layer 3) of PAH. 3. The deposit is 6cm – 8cm thick silty sand that overlaid the floor and the deposit of charcoal and ash. Without confirming the deposit in other areas of the monastic courtyard, its more generalized existence could not be verified.

But the presence of this deposit in PAH.3 might help us to propose that after the event of burning, a short-term sheet flood of low intensity affected the establishment.

Level VIII: Later periods of the main temple(Plates 34-35): We have already referred to the fact that Dikshit (1938: 13-15) had identified four construction periods above the second terrace of the central shrine. But it is not possible to correlate the levels identified by Dikshit with those we identified, owing to methodological disparity and modifications done by the later excavations, reconstructions, and restoration works. On the other hand, van Lohuizen-de Leeuw (1985) has dated the three construction periods of the monastery suggested by Dikshit (1938) to the end of eighth century, to the period between the late tenth and early eleventh century, and to the period between the late eleventh and early twelfth century. She did not elaborate upon the parameters on the basis of which the dating was proposed, however. Hence, her dates cannot be correlated to the dates of various periods of the main temple.

Interestingly enough, one of the latest occupational levels of the establishment is attested by several structures around the main temple that were built on such locations which indicate the abandonment of the pradakshinapatha of the first terrace, or on the ground level. Dikshit (1938), Lefèvre (2012) and Alam and Sultana (2013) have mentioned that the two square stupa on either side of the staircase of the main/central temple were constructed above the enclosure wall that determined the boundary of the circum ambulatory passage around the temple. The excavation conducted by Alam and Sultana (2013) confirms that. These two stupas, along with another temple and square stupa on the southern enclosure wall, block the circumambulatory passageway, denoting that this passageway was not used as it had been in the earlier periods. That also makes it evident that the stone sculptures at the plinth were buried at some later period when the passageway was abandoned.

It is quite clear that there is a deposit of more than 1.5m between this level and the level of the earliest floor. Without detailed excavation on each cardinal direction, it is not possible to detect the intermediate levels – that is, the levels corresponding to the entire occupational periods of the main temple; because of the modifications of deposits for the conservation and preservation works and poorly documented unsystematic excavations earlier, the extremely transformed deposits lack proper stratigraphic clues to the past. Yet, the reasons behind the raising of the ground level of the passageway and the courtyard are not clear. We think that raising the ground level up by 1.5m cannot only be

explained in terms of the gradual loss of significance of Brahmanical sculptures on the plinth level, as hinted at by Lefèvre (2012).

Taking into account the landscape context and frequency of floods recognized through our understanding of stratigraphy, one possible hypothesis could be that to continue with the activities of the establishment in the face of frequent flooding and consequent poor drainage and waterlogging, the raising up of the ground level was essential.

Dikshit (1938) found that the ‘original’ surface of the courtyard sloped gradually down from the southwest to the northeast. van Lohuizen-de Leeuw has confirmed the slope in the earliest occupation level (1985: 745). Dikshit did not talk about any outlets draining the water out from the courtyard, except for a few inside the courtyard (1938; Plate XXI). We are not sure about the existence of outlets or drains, even from the courtyard outside. Even the absence of any outlet does not necessarily prove that the conditions for good drainage remained the same throughout the occupational periods at the mahavihara.

What previous scholars, and consultants hired to solve the present waterlogging problem at Paharpur, have missed is the landscape setting on which the mahavihara establishment is located. They tried to solve the problem only in terms of the present courtyard. What we would like to propose here is certainly a hypothesis based on our geoarchaeological investigations outside the mahavihara. The stratigraphy in this paper also supports the proposition. The gradual vertical accretion of floodborn sediments both inside and outside the establishment, especially in relation to the gradual subsidence of the floodplain, in the pre-structural and structural periods is recognizable. The vertical accretion of the floodplain and contemporaneous dynamic lateral migrations of rivers from the east to west made it impossible to drain out the water from the courtyard. It was, therefore, necessary to raise the ground level of the courtyard.

Though we are skeptical about the possibility of retrieving the stratigraphic succession after the construction of the main temple, extensive excavation could be recommended around the main temple to get an idea of the succession of occupation before the construction of the main temple.

Level IX: Post excavation deposits and deposits, fillings and masonries of conservation and restoration activities:

This level includes masonry works, deposits and cuts of the post-excavation period that began in early 1920s. After the inclusion of the monuments as a world heritage site, many activities of excavation and relocation of deposits took place, specifically in the courtyard for solving the waterlogging problem. Most of the walls were completely taken out and have been rebuilt for the restoration work. The pits dug for these purposes and the re-filled deposits are included in this period.

LANDSCAPE CONTEXT OF THE SETTLEMENT: CHANNEL DYNAMICS AND FORMATIONS OF FLOODPLAIN

Alam and Sultana (2013) have already mentioned that the establishment was constructed upon the sandy alluvium of floodplain, instead of the Pleistocene uplifted tract popularly known as Barind. We have already shown in our discussion and interpretation of provisional stratigraphy and survey results that Somapura, or Dharmapaladeva Mahavihara, was not an isolated monument, and with all probability, there are monumental and habitational deposits in the surrounding area. The floodplain on which this seventh to eighth century CE settlement was constructed has been in flux since the mid-Holocene, at least. The present geomorphology and topography of the floodplain indicate that the dynamic state has been consistent through its history (see, fig 1 and 2 for the present geomorphic features of the landscape context). The most crucial point, then, is why was such a large settlement centering on a relatively huge monument established on a relatively unstable surface, when the relatively stable surface of the tract was available in the vicinity on the Barind? Another important aspect of the problem is the interaction of this settlement with the forms and processes of the floodplain, particularly with the lateral migration of the Chhoto Jamuna River system and antecedent courses of present Kata Jamuna River (or their antecedent courses with altogether different names). In order to understand and solve the problems, the alluvial geoaerchaeology of the spatial context of the Somapura Mahavihara establishment must be addressed. The establishment and the associated settlement are located almost at the distal part of a floodplain which is known as Teesta Meander Floodplain. At present, Chhoto Jamuna River with her tributaries drain the floodplain. The floodplain occupies a deep valley within the tectonically uplifted, and later eroded, Barind Terrace. The valley confinement is one of the key features of floodplain building processes, which, it seems, has begun since the early Holocene, according to Goodbred and Kuehl (2000), with the sediments in-filling because of the increase in the intensity of the southeast monsoon and concurrent increase in sediment supply. The nomenclature for different units of Barind Terrace in the maps of this paper has been used following the pedo-geomorphic classification by Sen (2012). The study area comprises three units. They are: 1. Narrowly dissected terrace with moderately to weakly developed soils (NDTMWS), 2. High terrace with moderately to strongly developed soils (HTMSS), 3. Gently rolling terrace with moderately to strongly developed soils (GRTMSS). Sen (2012) has classified the terrace on the basis of topography and rate of the development of soils. It is not necessary here to go into the details of these units, as they would be irrelevant. Yet, it must be noted that the terrace is at least 2-3m higher than the floodplain surface, and that the floodplain soils and sediments, in most cases, in the vertically onlap position at the edge of the terrace.

Following are the essential characterizations of the alluvial spatial context of the establishment.

Chhoto Jamuna River System (Fig 1 and 2; Plates 36-38): Jamuna River, now known as Chhoto Jamuna, and her tributaries are one of the most prominent river systems in the region. According to BWDB report (2005), her length, width and depth at present are 56km, 30m and 2m, respectively. It seems that Chhoto (or little) has been added as a prefix after the significant decrease in her flow regime in the twentieth century. Buchanon-Hamilton described the river as follows:

I next come to a much finer river, the Yomuna or Jomuna, a name which is common to several Indian rivers, and which has been variously corrupted by Europeans in Emona, Jomuna and Jubuna. It is a small river, with a gentle clear stream of considerable depth. Its water is considered as remarkably pure and wholesome, and its banks are richest part of the district, and are now little subject to injury from its floods. It has diminished in size since the water of the Stishta were turned to the eastward, and is now probably of the size just proper for fertilizing the soil, without injuring the crops. (1833:13)

As Buchanon-Hamilton suggested, the river has been transformed into an ephemeral stream. The main course is a slightly entrenched meandering channel, and at bank full stage her width varies from 20-35 meter. Presently, she carries local surface runoff during peak monsoon in July and August. Throughout rest of the year, her bed exposes thick sandy deposits with very few gravels. The channel is characterized by channel macroforms, both point bars and longitudinal bars. Various sizes of dunes on the bed surface and on the surface of the macroforms, and pool and riffle structures along with the thalweg, are principal features of the architecture. The depth of the channel is insignificant considering the large amount of sediment deposited on the bed every year, and these sediments put the channel into a continuous process of aggradations. It seems that seasonally active peak flow is characterized more by bed-load sediment. Apparently, the competence of the river has been reduced a lot since Buchanon-Hamilton's time.

The past competence of Chhoto Jamuna River (and her antecedent rivers) is attested by the vast floodplain created by the deposits carried through this river. The floodplain's width varies from 3.45km to 17.80km. This floodplain bears very important signatures of the lateral migration of Chhoto Jamuna River. Channel remnants, oxbow lakes, meander scrolls, crevasse splays and back-swamps mark the flood plain. Present habitations are located on the ridges of the plain. Apparently, the river has swung eastward and westward several times within the floodplain bounded by the Barind terrace on both sides. The floodplain can be termed as the zone of migration of Chhoto Jamuna River. The chronology of these shifts is not quite clear, yet by

corroborating the palaeo-channel remnants and archaeological records, it is possible to identify the courses and patterns of changes in some of the places.

Several prominent tributaries are included within the Chhoto Jamuna System. Chiri is a small stream that passes through the same floodplain as the main course of Chhoto Jamuna. BWDB report (2005) describes her having a length of 9 kilometers and width and depth of 30 meters and 2 meters, respectively. Although it has been said that she is originated from Jyot Sadhak Beel, surveying in the Dinajpur region (Sen 2012) shows that she comes out of the Chhoto Jamuna River in Phulbari and meets the same at Joypurhat sadar Upazila (Fig 1). Another stream comes out from the same spot of the convergence and continues to the southeast to meet Tulshiganga at Akkelpur Upazila. This channel is known as Kata Jamuna. Buchanon-Hamilton (1833) refers to the channel as an artificial one that was dug by the ancestor of a local rich merchant, Baidyonath Mondol, and he was the principle landholder of the area when Buchanon-Hamilton was there (1833: 14). The pattern of this channel suggests that it is not completely an artificial channel; rather a modified version of an earlier course, perhaps. Our surveying suggests that this channel is still known to the local people as Chiri.

Another stream rising from the Chhoto Jamuna River in Birampur Upazila comes down southwest of Chiri and meets the main course of Chhoto Jamuna at the border of present Badolgachhi and Dhamoirhat Upazila to the west of Somapura Mahavihara establishment (fig. 1). This channel is known as Ghagra in topographic maps of Survey of Bangladesh. Buchanon-Hamilton refers to this channel as Padmawoti and he mentioned that it is called also as Chiri by the locals. The river called Ghuski rises from Phulbari Upazila and passes parallel to the west side of Ghagra. This channel might have originated from Ichhamoti, a tributary of Atrai marking the border between West Bengal, India, and Bangladesh at the northwest corner of Phulbari Upazila, and she meets Chhoto Jamuna to the west of Somapura Mahavihara and towards the south of the confluence of Chhoto Jamuna and Ghagar (Fig 1). Buchanon-Hamilton (1833: 13-14) describes the channel as inundating its banks to a considerable extent and as navigable in all seasons for canoes and very small boats, and he contends that this course admits boats carrying 1000 mons as far as Kisorjunj. She is a meandering channel with low sinuosity at the upstream. Her sinuosity increases rapidly when she enters into West Bengal, India, and within the Chhoto Jamuna floodplain the sinuosity reaches the highest level. Her sinuosity decreases gradually at the downstream. Like all the other tributaries of Chhoto Jamuna River, this channel is moderately incised. In Rennell's map (1776), Ghuski is shown as originating from the present Phulbari Upazila area. Her possible connections to the Ichhamoti River to the west and the Chhoto Jamuna River to the east were cut off before Rennell's survey in the area.

The parallel drainage pattern of the Chhoto Jamuna River orients the system on north-south axis. The vast floodplain bounded at the east and west by comparatively consolidated sediments of Barind tract attests to the fact that the entire system was very competent to carry sediments from the Himalayan piedmont zone in the early-late Holocene period.

Teesta Meander Floodplain: The alluvial context of the Somapura Mahavihara and associated settlements are characterized by the Teesta Meander floodplain. Although the floodplain has been formed by the processes of the antecedent channels of present Chhoto Jamuna River, it has been named after the river Teesta because of the fact that, before the eighteenth century, Teesta flowed in a north-south direction and drained through several channels, including Chhoto Jamuna River, as shown in Rennell's map (1776). The shifting processes of the flow regimes of the Chhoto Jamuna River System are important for understanding Somapura Mahavihara establishment's relationship to the floodplain.

From various sources and research, it is evident now that the changes in Teesta and Brahmaputra were triggered not by a single cause. The dominance of a cause over the others, nevertheless, varied spatio-temporarily. Citing Brammer (1996) and Fergusson (1863), Goodbred et al. (2003: 307) suggested that severe earthquakes in the Sylhet region resulted in vertical displacements near Mymensingh. It had the initial impact on the avulsion of the Brahmaputra from its old course east of the Madhupur Tract to its modern channel.

Best et al. (2008) give a summary of the works on the changes in the course of the Brahmaputra-Jamuna River. They think that over the past 250 years, the course has changed dramatically. They added that there is evidence of both large-scale avulsion in the period 1776-1850 and a more general westward migration of the Jamuna channel belt since this date (2008: 399). They refer to Bristow (1999) who, according to them, presents 'the most recent summary of theories for the trigger of the change in channel belt location' (Best et al. 2008: 399). They added,

Prior to 1843, the Brahmaputeea flowed within the channel now termed the 'old Brahmaputra, east of the Madhupur tract, and joined Meghna river. Sometimes between 1830 and 1860, Bristow (1999) contends that avulsion of the river occurred, and caused a maximum 80km of lateral shifting of the river course from the east to the west of the Madhupur tract. (2008: 399)

These researchers suggested different causes contributing to the avulsion of Brahmaputra-Jamuna River course by citing different scholars. These causes are: tectonic activity (Winkley et al. 1994), switches in the upstream of the course of the Teesta River (Morgan and McIntire 1959), the influence of increased discharge (Coleman 1969), catastrophic floods (La Touche 1910) and river capture in an old river course (Bristow 1999). The most important point

made from an analysis of maps between 1776 and 1843 by Bristow (1999) is, in the words of Best et al. (2008):

The river avulsion was more likely gradual than catastrophic, and may have been generated by bank erosion, perhaps around a large mid-channel bar, causing diversion of the channel into an existing floodplain channel. The map of Rennel (1776) clearly shows a sequence of large bars near the offtake of what is now the Jumuna suggesting local sediment overload and diversion of flow against the banks (2008: 401).

They added (2008: 401) that several authors have also described the gradual westward migration of the Jumuna braidbelt (see, for example, Coleman 1969; Sarker 1996; Khan and Islam 2003).

Simultaneously, a change in the course of Teesta was caused by a great flood on the day of 27 August 1787. Rashid describes the event in the following way:

Considerable structural changes in Barind region affected the [Karatoya] which rapidly dwindled. Teesta with a large amount of water left over, could not pass down the Atrai without causing floods. The excessive rain of 1787 suddenly brought down a vast flood of sand and choked the Atrai channel, which the result that the Teesta burst into the very small Ghaghat river, and not finding sufficient outlet overflowed and swept nearly the whole of Rangpur district (1991: 46).

The changes in the river system did not happen instantaneously. The changes in the entire drainage pattern of the northwestern part of Bangladesh started, as far as the available historical accounts reveal, in around 1782. The changes described above reflect only those that can be known from the historical records. We must not assume that from the seventh or eighth century CE to the eighteenth century period, over a span of time of more than one thousand years, the river system remained the same. The innumerable geomorphic signatures on the floodplain signify the frequent changes of the courses of the Chhoto Jamuna River System along with the antecedent rivers even before the eighteenth century CE.

It is difficult to classify the Teesta Floodplain following the well-known genetic classification by Nanson and Croke (1992), as their classification incorporated models from other parts of the world. We may, nevertheless, borrow a few of the ideas and classifications from their work, as they perceive floodplain formation from the perspectives of multiple factors and processes, which lends an ingenious quality to their work compared to others (see for example, Thornbury 1969; Petts and Foster 1985; Lewin 1978; Leopold and Wolman 1957; Schumm 1968, 1977; Allen 1965; Galloway 1981). The Teesta Floodplain could be identified as a polyphase floodplain which has been formed by a slowly(?) migrating river, and in which the basal or distal parts of the floodplain may be a legacy of a prior flow regime, while the upper units or those proximal to the

channel are most likely to represent sediment transported and deposited by the present flow regime (Nanson and Croke 1992: 460). In the classification of floodplain by Nanson and Croke, where 'floodplains are best categorized genetically because of the interrelation between river processes and the floodplain they construct' (1992: 463), the Teesta Floodplain resembles the category 'B3b: Meandering river, lateral migration scrolled floodplains' which includes the sedimentary class of gravel, sand and silts and landforms of flat to undulating floodplain surface with distinct scrolled pattern, oxbows and backswamps (Nanson and Croke 1992: 467; Table 1). The depositional and erosional processes of this kind of floodplain, according to them, are cut-bank erosion, lateral point-bar accretion, overbank vertical and abandoned channel accretion, counterpoint accretion and minor oblique accretion.

In their elaboration of the later section of their paper, they have included this kind of floodplain into 'Class B: Medium-energy non-cohesive floodplains' (1992: 473). Nanson and Croke then go into detail on the processes of building this type of floodplain (1992: 476-77).

The problems with the inclusion of Teesta Meandering Floodplain into the categories devised by Nanson and Croke are as follows:

Firstly, valley confinement of this floodplain between the cohesive soils of the uplifted and eroded Barind terrace makes some of the processes more controlled. This particular variable attributes to this floodplain the forms and processes of a high energy non-cohesive floodplain, especially a confined vertical accretion sandy floodplain (Order A2; Nanson and Croke 1992: 470-472). Secondly, the presence of a large and linear back swamp, presently known as Malancha Beel, to the east of the present monumental remains attribute to it some of the characteristics of the sub-order B3c (Nanson and Croke 1992: 477).

The juxtaposition among various classes proposed by Nanson and Croke in reference to the Teesta Meandering floodplain, consequently, turns into a difficult problem of interpreting the floodplain formation processes. They are crucial for negotiating the interrelationship between the transformation of human settlement associated with the mahavihara and the transformation processes of the floodplain. We must accept, on the basis of the proposed stratigraphy of the Somapura Mahavihara, that floodplain processes and their history were crucial for the changes and continuity of the settlement here.

Formation processes of ridge and swale, and swamps and back swamps, as has been suggested by the topography of the floodplain, were very important for the history of settlement activity on this location. Lateral and vertical accretion along with counterpoint accretion played their part. But the problem lies in the question regarding whether the factors affecting these processes were gradual, as has

been attributed as a feature of the medium energy non-cohesive floodplains (see Nanson and Croke 1992: 476-477), or catastrophic, as they are often characterized as the high energy non-cohesive floodplains (see Nanson and Croke 1992: 470-472). The palaeochannel pattern along with signatures like channel remnants and ox-bow lakes indicate that the channels laterally migrated towards both the east and the west (see fig 1 and 2).

CORRELATION OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL AND GEOARCHAEOLOGICAL INTERPRETATIONS: IMPLICATIONS FOR CONCLUDING INFERENCES

Outcrops outside the mahavihara establishment, both inside and outside the tentative boundary of the settlement zone, exposed by the local people's digging and on accidental sections and showing tabular and trough cross bedding structures formed within channels (Plates 39-42; see Miall 1996) overlain by sandy massive vertical accretion units have been observed and recorded. They clearly refer to the dominance of the processes of lateral and vertical accretions in the formative history of the floodplain and the lateral migration of rivers as most significant processes of floodplain history. Besides, the data from the boreholes taken in the courtyard of the present ruins of the mahavihara in the report on the preparation of a master plan clearly depicts the vertical association of predominantly floodplain sediments (Sanday et al. 1983: 140-41; annexure 10). Panja et al. (2002) earlier referred to the alluvial context of Somapura Mahavihara in a brief manner.

The proposed stratigraphy suggests that floods of low to medium energy were regular and might have played their part in the changes in hydrological regimes and shifts in the channel processes, and consequent shifts in hydrological regimes. Concurrently, if the flood cycles in Bengal are considered, there is a trend of huge floods within 5- to 10-year periods without any impact from other factors (e.g. seismic effect, etc.). For the moment, nevertheless, we must not put aside both the catastrophic and gradual nature of the processes (see Figs 1 and 2) whatever the propagating factors might be. Historically, on any temporal scale these two types can converge quite regularly and they often cannot be separated with distinctive signatures on the floodplain morphology.

Another problem demands special attention. The proposed stratigraphy suggests that the first settlement was constructed on a surface that is presently 3.5-4.5m below the present floodplain surface (see Fig 6). In fact, the earliest occupational deposits represent a very important clue regarding the geomorphological history of the floodplain in relation to the history of habitations on the terrain. The altitudinal level of the earliest settlement on this location could be considered as normal and its location as buried deposits could have been identified within a normal burial of the remains of a settlement under deposits of regular flooding. But at present, even during the dry months of

March and April, the ground water table is just 3m-3.5m below the present surface, given the fact that there has been a gradual lowering of the ground water table during the past three decades, in particular, because of the over-exploitation of ground water for irrigation purposes and rapid drying up of the rivers. It is evident that since the shifting of the Brahmaputra and Teesta Rivers, there have been gradual declines in the regional rivers and their intakes. Interventions during the colonial period and during post-independence periods, including flood management projects by different types of dams and controls on the rivers of the region, have transformed the hydrological characters of the region, including the channel geometry and flow regimes, to a great extent. Existence of a flood-free surface with a ground water table at a much lower depth seems improbable. The earliest habitational remains at the depth/level at which they have been detected in the small trenches could be explained in terms of following probabilistic inferences:

First, it could be interpreted that the surface has tectonically subsided. Neotectonic activities are common in this zone. In the research of Jahan and Ahmed (1997), it has been suggested that the present Chhoto Jamuna River and a few other rivers are on lineaments. Rashid (2011) has shown that there is N-S trending lineament along the river near Joypurhat. Recent geophysical studies, moreover, have shown that there are basement faults with horst and graben structures because of these faults. For example, GSI (2000) identified that the Malda-Kishanganj fault, having approximately N-S trend, passes through the west of the study area. A cluster of depressions to the south of Naogaon indicates subsidence, and they might be the result of neotectonic activity. Structurally, the area lies on the southern slope of the Rangpur saddle, which slopes towards the southeast. The slow upliftment of Barind tract is a consistent and current phenomenon as has been shown in various studies (e.g., Coates et al. 1988; Alam 1995). Recent vertical movements were at the rate of 0.4 to 1.1mm/year (Haque 1982: 177). Jahan and Ahmed (1997: 750) have also suggested that, 'The relief, topography and drainage of the area are controlled by the neotectonic activities which are reflected from the present geomorphic conditions of the area.' The shifting of Bramapurta River and Teesta River in the eighteen century, besides, indicates the active tectonics in the area. If the very recent seismicity is considered, concentration of epicentres paralleling 88° E longitude can be observed, suggesting a weak zone. The adjoining area had experienced a shaking effect from the Nepal-Bihar earthquake of 1934 (Roy 1839). The gradual upliftment of the adjacent Barind surface because of neotectonism, along with the subsidence of the floodplain, could be an explanation of the existence of the occupational layer at such a depth, and also the lateral shifts of channels described below as the third argument (see, Schumm et al. 2000).

Second, the habitations occupied ridges/levees of the floodplain with a relative equilibrium state with a ground water table at least one meter below the present level. More research on ground water level changes during the Late Holocene period could substantiate this argument in the future.

Third, the floodplain oscillated in a cyclical equilibrium fashion, at least up to the construction of the present monastic establishment, in response to short-term periods of several decades dominated by floods or droughts (Nanson and Erskine 1988, cited in Nanson and Croke 1992: 461). It does not mean that after the construction of the present mahavihara complex and the settlement the floodplain was in a continuous equilibrium state, as far as the sedimentological and geomorphological evidence suggest. In accordance to these data, we contend that the occurrences of floods were a normal phenomenon, and the lateral shifting of the river towards the west and the east was a process that continued beyond the abandonment of the settlement. At the same time, periodic occurrences of huge floods were also a persistent event in this geomorphologic context.

Processes described in the first and the third points probably acted together along with the latest anthropogenic processes to give the floodplain context of its present form.

On the basis of recently deciphered and interpreted epigraphic evidences, a continuity of the riverine landscape could be envisaged. In the Indian Museum Copper Plate Inscription of Dharmapala, year 26, donation of land plots for a viharika and a perfume chamber (ghandhakuthi) established by mahasamanta Bhadranaga and his consort at (or close to) Somapura Mahavihara was recorded (Furui 2011: 145-56). This land grant supports our claim that Somapura Mahavihara was not an isolated monument as it is widely recognized. The boundary of the land donated for the viharika was demarcated by one of the viharika, and they were not within the present structural remains that are identified as the Somapura Mahavihara, as attested by the currently preserved monumental remains. Rather, these two structures were close, we suppose, to the monument, according to the description of this inscription. The description, as Furui has already suggested, indicates that Somapura Mahavihara was not composed of the present single-unit monumental remains identified as the mahavihara itself. All the monuments of that mahavihara were not constructed by Dharmapala. The observation of Furui must be taken into account:

In view of the structure of Somapura Mahavihara represented by the present site of Paharpur, it is remarkable that a monastic complex mostly constituted by a single gigantic structure had a character as composite as Nalanda's. The later consists of multiple monastic compounds. The composite character may be a clue to the difference between mahavihara and vihara as categories (2011: 151).

No published works on the Nalanda Mahavihara establishment have attended to the hinterland zone of the mahavihara.⁶ It is not possible to say whether several viharas formed a cluster here like Nalanda or not. But it could be argued on the basis of the above inscription that Somapura Mahavihara was not an isolated monument as identified by van Lohuizen-de Leeuw (1985: 742). Somapura Mahavihara, we contend, emerged as the core of a settlement zone on a dynamic alluvial context. While taking into account the differences between mahavihara, vihara and viharika as different categories for which a singular term like 'monastery' is inadequate⁷, it could be contended that the composite establishment, along with its hinterland zone with other habitational remains, could be even larger than we have delineated in this study through our survey (see, Fig 2). Hossain's reference to Sonarpara Bhita (Hossain 2004) - an archaeological settlement covering roughly two hector area and lying 3 km to the east of the monumental remains - suggests the possibility of the extension of the hinterland zone of the main settlement towards the east and to other directions as well. This zone has been shown in figure 2 as the hypothetically extended settlement zone.

In the same copper plate inscription (Furui 2011), we may find reference to the donation of a landplot to a vihara constructed by Bhadranaga and his consort. The description of this first land plot and its boundaries could also be very suggestive for our interpretation of past landscape and location of river courses. The description is as follows:

The first plot is a flat land tract (talapataka) of a vihara constructed by mahasamanta Bhadranaga in the village of Antaravanika belonging to the Snanita-mandala in Kotivarsa-visaya of Pundravardhana-bhukti (ll. 29-30). The landmarks demarcating its borders are described as follows: to the east, a half stream (ardha-srtota) of the river named Cirika, to the south the border of the northern side (Uttara-yaga) of the pond (puskarini) of Rahayyaditya, to the west, a half stream of the river Pravara; to the north, the southern border of a flat land tract of Bhadranaga's viharika (ll.30-32) (2011: 146-47).

The crucial contribution of the description is the demarcation of the landmarks, especially by the half-stream Cirika and Pravara. It is difficult to locate the village of Antaravanika without detailed surveying in a wide area. But we have already mentioned in the previous section that a small tributary of present Chhoto Jamuna River is known as Chiri. She comes out of the Chhoto Jamuna River in the northern part of Birampur Upazila and meets Chhoto Jamuna in Joypurhat Sadar Upazila towards the north of Somapura Mahavihara (fig. 1). We think that present Chiri still bears the name of Chirika. Careful analyses of the palaeo channel styles and patterns, along with the palaeo channel remnants (i.e. the orientation of the oxbow lakes), indicate that present course of Chiri had maintained her

course at least in Joypurhat Sadar Upazila. She flowed towards the west of present Kata Jamuna River, known popularly as Chiri. Thus Pch 4 or Pch 5 (Fig. 8). could be the Chirika River during the earlier part of ninth century, the issuance period of the aforementioned copper plate inscription.

At the same time, fifth Damodarpur copper plate inscription of 214 G.E. (c. 533-34 CE) mentions the location of the donated land to the east of Jambunadi (Basak 1919: 144). Damodarpur is located now in Phulbari Upazila of Dinajpur District and A. K. M. Zakariah has already tentatively identified the antecedent courses of the present Chhoto Jamuna River in Phulbari and Birampur Upazilas as the Jambunadi (Jambu River) referred to in this inscription (2011: 142). Considering that the name of the river had not changed along with the changes in the courses of the river in the less than three hundred years between the dates of the issuance of these two copper plates, the present channel of Chhoto Jamuna in the Joypurhat Sadar Upazila and Pch 6 (see, Fig. 8) could be identified as the Jambunadi. It must be noted that to the north of Joypurhat Upazila, Chhoto Jamuna River shows signs of lateral migration towards the east and the west in different locations of her course, and one of the courses [as in the case of a palaeochannel in the north of Birampur Upazila suggested by Zakariah (2011: 142)] was known as Jambunadi. This part of the course has not been shown in the maps in this paper. It could be proposed, therefore, that Jambunadi flowed to the north and the west of Somapura Mahavihara, and that Chrika River was one of her tributaries. On the basis of the patterning of the palaeochannel courses and remnants, it could also be hypothesized that present Ghagra River (Fig. 1) had her antecedent course towards the east of the present course. Pch. 7 (see, Fig. 8) close to the Chirika River (the area covered by the flow of Chiri River before her present confluence with Chhoto Jamuna or Jambu River) was probably known as the half-stream Pravara mentioned in the above description of the donated land plot in the copper plate inscription of the time of Dharmapala. The location of the donated land in the village Antaravanika, therefore, could be anywhere in between these two courses on the Teesta meander floodplain, as it has been identified as 'flat-land'. The land was probably situated somewhere in the area, the southern boundary of which lay at least 7-10km to the north of the monumental remains of Somapura Mahavihara. Mahasamanta Bhadranaaga's dominion, in this way, covered that area from the present Joypurhat Sadar Upazila to the area lying north of it.

Here, the mention of these rivers as half-streams clearly signifies that these channels were ephemeral at that time, and the processes and conditions of shifting of the rivers in the vicinity of Somapura Mahavihara were prevailing during the occupational period of present establishment. We must,

however, presume that they were not completely abandoned at that time in the earlier part of the ninth century CE. It would be relevant indeed to note that Taranatha's account referred to the construction of Somapura Mahavihara in a lake (Chimpa and Chattopadhyaya 1970: 266). According to the account, the lake was dried by a supernatural creature and eventually the monastery was built there.⁸ Even if the inconsistency and inaccuracy of Taranatha's account is considered, the present geomorphology of the landscape context of the mahavihara indicates that an alluvial terrain with swamps (lakes, in Taranatha's words) could have existed during the construction period of the mahavihara and associated settlement. The story could get firm historical basis if the event of flooding and consequent inundation in our proposed stratigraphy before the construction of the monumental remains are taken into account.

Under these circumstances, it is now possible to make an attempt, we think, to verify the arguments offered by Alam et al. (2008 and 2009). In spite of the fact that these two papers are rare examples of palaeoenvironmental studies through application of scientific techniques in association with the monumental remains in Bangladesh's archaeology, their conclusions are seemingly overgeneralized and spurious. On the basis of clay mineralogy of collected samples from two trenches inside and outside the mahavihara, they concluded that:

during the period from the middle of the eighth to late tenth century, Paharpur and adjoining areas experienced a generally cool climate, i.e. the temperature remained slightly below 0°C. Then around the late eleventh century, the temperature rose slightly above 0°C. This warming trend within a generally cool temperature regime continued and in the early twelfth century (1100 A.D.), the temperature increased slightly more. This increase may be the beginning of a medieval warm period....These observations are consistent with the X-ray diffraction study of these archaeological soils, which means that both the clay mineralogical data and the past changes in global temperature curves echo the presence of generally cool to temperate and dry climates at Paharpur and adjoining regions from around the middle of the 700 to early 1100 A. D. (2008: 1649).

The analyses of Phytoliths from the samples of the same trench were, Alam et al. (2009: 511) claimed, 'in close agreement with the clay mineralogical data from Paharpur.' They have also tentatively proposed an alteration between El Niño and La Niña, between reduced rainfall causing crops to fail and severe flooding (Alam et al. 2009: 510). They have also presented four calibrated radiocarbon dates from the samples collected from the two trenches and the dates corroborate with the occupational periods of Somapura Mahavihara (Alam et al. 2009: 508; Table 2).

Fig. 8: The tentative patterning of palaeochannels and hypothesized course of Cirika and Pravara Rivers according to Furui (2011) and Jambu River according to Basak (1919)

The interpretation of palaeoenvironmental and palaeoclimatic conditions around Somapura Mahavihara during its occupational period do not fit into the interpretations of data we have presented in this paper. We think that the basic problem with the interpretations above hinges on the conceptual and methodological framework, not with the techniques that have been applied. The treatment of archaeological sediments from the deposits of a structural complex cannot be the same as the treatment of purely non-anthropogenic sediments. In these cases, the authors have claimed to reach the first occupational level of the monastic establishment at the depth of 150 cm in trench 1 and 138 cm in trench 2. The interpretations of the data presented here clearly exhibit that the deposits pertaining to first occupational level of even of the present monastic establishment lie deeper, and it is contrary to the

identification of Barind clay residuum as present in the lower and upper zone (Alam et al. 2008: 1641-42 and 2009: 506). In our analysis and proposed stratigraphy, we have shown that the entire establishment was constructed on the late Holocene sandy floodplain alluvium, and there is no possibility of the presence of Barind clay residuum even as detrimental sediments. The locations of the trenches, furthermore, suggest that they were dug into the filling of the pits that had been excavated earlier for the preservation and restoration of monastic walls. It has already been stated here that the deposits within the courtyard and outside the monastic walls have been modified and relocated through many excavations and diggings, both systematic and unsystematic, since Dikhsit's time, specifically for conservation work and for solving the waterlogging problems.

Contextually relocated secondary archaeological deposits cannot be treated as primary for any generalizations on any issues pertaining to the occupational history and associated environmental history. Corroboration of radiocarbon dates to the known chronology of the monumental remains does not necessarily correspond to the contextual reliability of the analyzed samples from archaeological deposits. The interpretation of palaeoclimatic condition, as a consequence, generates a conjecture as improbable as a cool climate below 0°C. The garments on the secular figures of terracotta plaques on the central temple, besides, do not suggest this very cold temperature.

The tentative and proposed stratigraphy and its geoarchaeological implications that have been elaborated upon in this paper have pointed at conditions controlled by the landscape rather than by the climate. The dynamic alluvial landscape presumably dominated by the lateral migration of rivers might have contributed to a significant extent to the transformations in occupational history of Somapura Mahavihara establishments. Floods, possibly both catastrophic and regular, were key factors, at least for the pre-structural period. For the structural periods, we may assume on reliable ground that floods played a significant role in the configuration and re-configurations of life ways and human-landscape interaction during the eighth century to thirteenth century CE period.

The reconceptualization of floods is essential in this respect. Panja (2003) has shown that 'monuments' in the flood zones in the Varendri region had differential interconnections with the builders and recipients, both functionally and symbolically. The 'monuments' and their symbolic interconnections with the patrons, builders and recipients on a flood-prone landscape context thus indicate that it is misleading to think that 'monuments' were built only on the landscapes that were flood-free. Rather, the role of monuments as institutions must be rethought.

In these ways, Sen (2012) has inferred that Buddhist viharas acted as the core of settlement structure and patterns in Varendri region during the period after c. eighth century CE. It has also been postulated by Sen (2012) that Buddhist mahavihara/vihara/viharikas as the core of settlements were not essentially the centre of disciplined austere religious practice and learning of renunciant Buddhist monks or religious activities of Buddhist samghas (see, Schopen 2010 and Almond 1988 for illuminating elaborations on Indian Buddhism and Schopen 1991 for the problem of religion as an object of inquiry in Indian Buddhism). Rather, he added, these Buddhist establishments acted as active agents in socio-economic and socio-political formations and mobilizations (See also, Jha 2003). Thus, it is necessary to rethink the established notion of Buddhist samgha and its relation to the laity. He has shown that during the period after c. eighth century CE, Buddhist establishments were important agents in the expansion of settlements, peasantization and agrarian frontier in Varendri region.

Somapura Mahavihara and associated settlements in its hinterland zone situated in a dynamic alluvial terrain close to the uplifted Barind terrace, if they are perceived and interpreted from these perspectives, could be another important archaeological locus in support of the inferences by Sen (2012) (See, Banarjee 2013 for pointing out the relation of the Samgha of Nalanda Mahavihara with agricultural and trade).

The proposed stratigraphy clearly hints at the idea that the pre-structural periods of the settlement here were a time when the dynamisms in the hydrology and landscape were not in some kind of hiatus. Rather, the settlement activities took place probably to exploit the floodplain environment. It has already been proposed that the first habitation in this place could not be dated before the sixth or seventh centuries CE. We have to keep in mind that the changes in channel and hydrological regimes in this region might have a temporal scale from a decade to several centuries. In spite of the fact that activities during these periods seem to have halted because of floods, the strategy to adapt with the regular seasonal floods is more or less evident. The floods that compelled the inhabitants to abandon the settlement temporarily or to halt occupational activities must have been with a larger extent and strength. It would be fallacious to contend that during the occupation of the mahavihara the rivers and the landscape were stable, as has been proposed earlier. The mahavihara with such stature and prominence and the earlier structure were established here probably because of the religious significance of the place. Especially, the Somapura Mahavihara was established after either the destruction or abandonment of an earlier religious 'monument' because – among other possible reasons still to be identified – of the sacred importance of this place, which also rendered the act of building the mahavihara a representation of the authority and power of the builders and the patrons.

The agricultural potential of the floodplain with recent alluvium is greater than that of the adjacent uplifted terrace of Barind. If the Somapura Mahavihara is perceived and addressed as the 'core' of a settlement or several settlements rather than as singular 'monument' or 'monument complex', then the interconnection between the inhabitants and the landscape becomes more comprehensible in terms of the proposed relation between agrarian expansion and Buddhist vihara and samgha. Four interesting brick-built structures in the courtyard of the present monumental remains have been identified by Alam and Sultana (2013: 18) - probably with justification - as the places where crops were piled up (Plates 43-46). These structures offer us some idea about the role samgha played in the management of agricultural products, even if it was for their own consumption. The donated land to the vihara of mahasamanta Bhadranaaga – as the description above shows – was a flatland. It indicates that the land was probably used for agriculture, and that the products or the exchanged values of the produced crops were used for

the sustenance and maintenance of the vihara. It must be pointed out, as Sen (2012) has argued, that the maintenance and sustenance of Somapura Mahavihara along with the other vihara, mahavihara and viharika of the sub-region were not essentially and solely dependent upon direct royal patronage. The lands donated by royal patrons as well as by various samanta and other groups from the laity transformed these establishments, often into large-scale landholders (see, Furui 2007; Sen 2012). Under these circumstances, Sen (2012) added, it is quite unlikely that Buddhist samgha could have acted in isolation and remained detached from the management of these lands and agrarian production. The complex articulations of authority and power among various stake-holders – samgha, royal patrons, samantas, different classes of peasants – must be sorted out to verify this hypothesis. At the same time, the role of local and sub-regional networks of samghas and viharas for land and agricultural product management must be addressed seriously on the basis of archaeological, ge archaeological, epigraphic and textual data in future research.

Our findings in this paper force us to think beyond the stereotyped role and functions of Buddhist samghas in early medieval Varendri. For example, it is evident that the settlement or settlements around Somapura Mahavihara had to devise strategies for dealing with regular floods in an alluvial context in which rivers were consistently changing their courses. In this case, floods must not be conceptualized only as a disaster to be controlled and mitigated. Rather, in the pre-colonial agrarian frontiers of Bengal, floods were one of the essential modalities to augment and maintain the fertility of the alluvial plain. The agrarian production and economy depended heavily upon riverine landscapes and floods. This is not to say that floods had not brought misery to the people and their life ways and people did not need to negotiate with the floods. However, the ideals, terms and practices of the negotiation were completely different than in modern flood management programmes. The management of irrigation, besides, was another essential aspect of the complex agrarian management schemes. What was the role of Buddhist samgha in the negotiation with the flood? We cannot simply deny their agency. But without more evidence, their roles in this particular aspect cannot be enumerated with specific details.

There are several tanks in and around the Somapura Mahavihara settlement boundary. These tanks played their role along with rivers in both habitational and irrigational activities. Sen (2012) has already shown that in early medieval Varendri, the settlement structure was determined by the spatial organization of artificial water bodies or tanks. By interpreting the spatial patterns of tanks and settlements, he has shown, it is possible to understand the significance of tanks in the habitational and irrigation system. But the tanks contributed in irrigation in different ways with regard to the particular landscape settings of the

settlements. The numbers of tanks are fewer around and within the settlements of Somapura Mahavihara than in many of the contemporary settlements on the uplifted terrace area (see, Sen 2012). In this case, for the settlements on the uplifted terrace with less soil permeability and water retention capacity, the contribution of tanks in irrigation was more elaborate and essential than in the settlements in the alluvial context, where land was regularly flooded and nourished, and the fertility of soil was greater. Taking this micro-scale variability in landscape and associated agricultural potential into account, the functioning of settlements developed around the large and small Buddhist establishments like those pertaining to Somapura Mahavihara and other vihara and viharika and their dynamic role in relation to the landscape can be envisaged.

The generalized explanations about the factors and processes involved in the abandonment of the settlement in terms of a vague notion of ‘decay’ in the Buddhism and Islamic expansion and iconoclasm in this part of South Asia, are required to be re-addressed. van Lohuizen-de Leeuw has already postulated that the relative paucity of images and ritual objects, and absence of the relics of funerary stupas in the last occupation layer, indicate the abandonment of the mahavihara before the arrival of Muslim armies (1985: 742-43). The excavation by Dikshit and later excavations (Alam 2004; van Lohuizen-de Leeuw 1985) showed that the size of monastic cells went through shifts in different periods. Alam (2004: 52-53) has shown that there is an earlier period below the monastic cells described by Dikshit. The earlier cells measured 4.87m × 3.96m and they were larger than the monastery of the later period. It seems, therefore, that the number of cells increased in the later period, indicating the increase of population of the establishment. On the other hand, Dikshit’s report (1938: 34-35) suggests that the monastic cells were transformed into private chapels, and pedestals were added in many cells during the later period. Consequently, the capacity of accommodation was reduced to a considerable extent. According to Dikshit, ‘it is clear that while the original monastery was designed for the occupation of 600 to 800 monks, not more than 400 monks may have lived in the monastery during the second period or about eleventh century A.D.’ (1938: 34). On around eleventh century CE, there was a noticeable decrease in the population in the mahavihara (see, also Gill 2007: 172). It is not possible right now to correlate the burning activity attested by the first occupational period of the central shrine and the first shifts in size of monastic cells. This possibility, however, cannot be ruled out. In this way, on the other hand, we may think that during the attack or after the attack on the mahavihara, according to the inscription of Vipulasrimitra, the population of this monastery was already decreased to a considerable extent. The notion of abandonment, therefore, has to be rethought with a new look at the evidence.

By going beyond monument-centrism, the microscale heterogeneity of factors and processes need to be addressed

for an understanding of the gradual loss of significance of the place. Dikshit (1938: 6) identified a possible Brahmanical edifice of fifteenth-sixteenth century at the southeast corner of the mahavihara. He referred to the existence of this temple, known as Gandheshwari Temple (Plate 47), as evidence of the casual visits of temporary sojourners. There is also a Ghat (landing stage), known as Sandhyabatir Ghat, to the east of the monastery which Hossain (2004) dated to the same period of Gandheshwari Temple. He thinks that the existence of the ghat suggests that there was a body of water in the vicinity of the remains to the east, and that it was active in the later period during the use of the ghat. Hossain refuted Dikshit's proposition about the existence of a 1.61 km wide river near the monastery, as the remains of the Tara Temple are 200m to the east of the monastery. Most importantly, the impact of floods as the cause of the abandonment has been referred to by Hossain (2004: 48). He offered several proposals which are as follows:

First, a devastating flood occurred around the twelfth-thirteenth century CE, causing the depopulation and siltation of the entire area. Second, the area remained waterlogged for a long time after this flood, and the central temple sunk below the original reddish clayey surface of the land. Third, after the recession of the flood water, various water channels and marshes were created, and one of the channels took the form of a river around the fourteenth-fifteenth centuries CE. Fourth, most of the remains of the settlements were washed away, except those in the northeastern and southern part. And fifth, sporadic smaller settlements of obscure and deviating origin started to grow in the vicinity of the monumental remains around the fourteenth-fifteenth centuries CE. Derelict structural ruins of the Sandhyabatir Ghat and Gandheshwari Temple belong to these settlements of the later period.

At first sight Hossain's propositions seem very attractive, in the sense that they bring to the fore some ideas that are not usually dealt with in the dominating views. In the light of our interpretations of stratigraphy and geoarchaeological elucidations, many of his arguments seemingly stem from an inadequate understanding of the landscape context of the settlements. The proposition of a 'devastating' flood around the thirteenth-fourteenth centuries cannot simply be ruled out, considering the stratigraphy and landscape context. The dating could be debatable in the absence of proper chronometric markers and stratigraphic evidence. But most of the other propositions become improbable on the basis of the geomorphological context and history of the landscape. For example, palaeochannels are the essential characteristics of the concerned landscape. There is no evidence of the destruction of the settlements during that particular period. Archaeological materials in the alluvial context, moreover, are not necessarily washed away by floods. In many cases, they could have gotten buried as has been found in our proposed stratigraphy. His chronometric relationship

between the ghat and the temple has no evidential foundation. Our observations on stratigraphy and geomorphology have shown that deposition, erosion and relative stability have continuously been temporally and spatially varied in the floodplain context of the settlements, as is always the case for floodplain depositional environments. There is no evidence of the sinking of the central temple and of reddish clayey soil in the floodplain environment. It has already been referred to the evidence that the surface of the courtyard was raised up. The interpretations of the gradual subsidence of the floodplain and concomitant upliftment of the terrace have already been mentioned. Evidence of later habitations does not wither away the possibility of losing the importance of the settlement. Along with other socio-religious and political factors and processes, the shift in the local channel pattern and hydrological regimes because of the gradual migration of the antecedents of the channels of the present Chhoto Jamuna River System towards the west must have caused the settlement here to be abandoned to a certain extent. The process of final abandonment could have started in the thirteenth century, but the monumental complex and the settlement were not completely abandoned. A few of the residing monk probably stayed in the place until the fourteenth-fifteenth centuries CE. The religious orientations of these monks cannot be determined. They could have maintained their identity or were converted and assimilated into dominant brahmanical communities. At the same time, they might have transformed into minor cult groups such as, Nera-Neris. The networks of these settlements, for example, with the Halud Vihara⁹, 10km to the south of the present monuments and several settlements in Kshetlal Upazila 10km – 15km to the east (see, Sen 2012), must be considered in the understanding of the various factors and processes of the biography and networks of these settlements. The causes and processes pertinent to landscape variables, under these circumstances, must be included as extremely significant.

End notes

1. Unit 1: (0-60cm) Surface deposit, greyish sandy silt
- Unit 2: (60-120cm) Greyish sandy silt with few brick bats and potsherds
- Unit 3: (120 – 168cm) Dark grey sandy silt with moderate pot sherds and brick-bats
- Unit 4: (168 – 190cm) Frequent dumped potsherds in greyish sandy silt
- Unit 5: (190-236cm) irregular and frequent brick fragments
- Unit 6: (236 – 260 cm) partially preserved brick-built structure
- Unit 7: (260 – 284cm) Dark grey silty loam mixed with charcoal and ash
- Unit 8: (284 – 296cm) Yellowish grey silty loam with frequent potsherds

Unit 9: (296 – 320cm) Dark grey silty loam with frequent potsherds the size of which is larger than the unit 8.

Unit 10: (320 – 360cm) Yellowish grey fine to medium sand with flat-bedded potsherds and few brick-bats.

2. Exploratory excavations at Paharpur after the independence have been listed in Hossen and Alam (2003).

3. See, Sircar (1970) for the reading of Jagadishpur Copper Plate inscription.

4. van Lohuizen-de Leeuw (1985) has referred to the excavations in 1981-82. Alam (2004b), on the other hand, has mentioned the excavations during 1982-1985.

5. Clay sealings from the excavation bear the inscription – Sri-Somapure Dharmapaladeva-mahavihariy-arya-bhikhsu-sangghasya meaning the noble community of bhiksus belonging to mahavihara of Dharmapaladeva at Somapura (Dilshit 1938: 90)

6. The existence of a considerably huge hinterland zone can indirectly be discerned from several sources. For example, the epigraphic records suggest the existence of many villages and markets (hatta) in the hinterland zone of Nalanda Mahavihara (Banerjee 2013). I-tsing stayed for several years in this mahavihara and referred to more than two hundred villages on the land in the possession of the establishment (Takakusu 1998). Recently, analysis of satellite imagery by M. B. Rajani has pointed to the existence of a large hinterland zone of the mahavihara (Rajani 2014).

7. The reference to three categories - mahavihara, vihara and viharika – are available from the epigraphic and textual sources. [see, for example, Indian Museum CPI of Dharmapala (Furui 2011) mentions both vihara and viharika. Jagadishpur CPI of 128 Gupta Era has a Buddhist vihara as one of the donees (Sircar 1970), Paharpur CPI referred to vihara of arhats (Dikshit 1929), The Ashrafpur CPIs refer to both vihara and viharika (Laskar 1904-07), Devaparvata CPI of Bhavadeva mentions Vendamati viharika as its donee (Sircar 1951), Gunaighar CPI of Vainyagupta mentions Avalokitesvarasramavihara constructed by Rudradatta (I.4), cultivated land (ksetra) of Rajavihara (II.19, 22), the border of agricultural land belonging to vihara of acarya Jitasena, Sakyabhiksu (Bhattacharya 1930), Jayarampur CPI of Gopachandra mentions the construction of a vihara in Bodhipadraka Mahavihara (Rajaguru 1976)] It seems that mahavihara is bigger and could be a constellation of small vihara. There is confusion regarding the nature of viharika. It could be small vihara as has been referred to by Furui (2011: 145). As has been suggested by Kaushik (2014) from the context of Sanghol, Punjab, viharika might be vihara for Bhikhunis (or nuns). It is impossible, however, at this moment to clearly identify the structural and functional attributes of a viharika. We must acknowledge, nevertheless, that they were separate categories with distinct nature. The term ‘monastery’ cannot be inclusive enough to attend to the heterogeneity.

8. The description is as follows: In the night, however, the five-headed Naga king appeared before him [Devapala] and said, ‘ I am your father. I shall drain the lake dry so that you can build there. Arrange for grand weekly offerings there.’ This was done and in twentyone days the lake got dried up and monastery was built (Chimpa and Chattopadhyaya 1970: 266).

9. Miah and Musa (2011) have identified the excavated remains of Halud Vihara as a Buddhist vihara. We have strong doubt about their identification. The main excavated structure is a Buddhist temple. However, the remains that have been identified as the wings of vihara are not possibly the wings. Rather, on the basis of our survey we think that the temple is an isolated one. The remains of the vihara could be somewhere else in the vicinity.

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বিষয়সংক্ষেপ

বিশ্বঐতিহ্য হিসাবে স্বীকৃত সোমপুর মহাবিহার নিয়ে হওয়া গবেষণার সংখ্যা কম নয়। বিখ্যাত গবেষক গ্রেগরি শোপেন এবং রবিন কনিংহাম দক্ষিণ এশিয়ার বৌদ্ধধর্ম এবং সংশ্লিষ্ট প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক ও ঐতিহাসিক অভীক্ষার পদ্ধতিগত ও মতাদর্শিক সীমাবদ্ধতা নিয়ে আলাপ করেছেন। প্রধানত টেকস্ট নির্ভর ব্যাখ্যার মধ্য দিয়ে দক্ষিণ এশিয়ায় বৌদ্ধধর্ম সম্পর্কিত কতগুলো ধারণা ঔপনিবেশিক সময় থেকেই উৎপাদিত হচ্ছে। এই ধারণাগুলো এখনো শক্তিশালী ও প্রচলিত। প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক ও অভিলেখতাত্ত্বিক গবেষণার লক্ষ্য থাকে ওই শক্তিশালী বয়ানগুলোর সমর্থন প্রদান করা। আলোচ্য গবেষকদ্বয় সহ আরো অনেকেই বৌদ্ধধর্ম সংশ্লিষ্ট প্রত্নতত্ত্ব চর্চার এই সীমাবদ্ধতা অতিক্রম করার চেষ্টা করেছেন। সামঞ্জস্যপূর্ণভাবে আমরা লক্ষ্য করি, পাহাড়পুরের সোমপুর মহাবিহার নিয়ে অধিপতিশীল ঐতিহাসিক ও প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক জ্ঞান প্রধানত স্থাপত্যবিদ্যা ও শিল্পকলার ইতিহাসে কেন্দ্রীভূত। সোমপুর মহাবিহার এবং তার স্থাপত্য, পোড়ামাটির ফলক, প্রস্তর ভাস্কর্যের শিল্পকলাগত ও ঐতিহাসিক দিক, এগুলোতে সামাজিক ও অন্যান্য বিষয়াবলির চিত্রন, মূর্তিতাত্ত্বিক দিক ইত্যাদি নিয়ে পণ্ডিতদের এসব আলোচনা সবিশেষ গুরুত্বপূর্ণ হলেও, বেশিরভাগ আলাপই আসলে প্রবলভাবে মনুমেন্ট-কেন্দ্রিকতায় সীমাবদ্ধ। এই প্রবন্ধে মনুমেন্ট-

কেন্দ্রীকতাকে অতিক্রম করার চেষ্টা করা হয়েছে প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক জরিপ, সাম্প্রতিক প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক খননের আলোকে স্তরবিন্যাসের ব্যাখ্যা, ভূপ্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক উপাত্তের বিশ্লেষণ এবং অভিলেখবিদ্যাগত উপাত্তের সমন্বিত ব্যবহারের মাধ্যমে। সংক্ষেপে বলা যেতে পারে যে, সোমপুর মহাবিহার কোনোভাবেই একটি বিচ্ছিন্ন একক স্থাপনা ছিল না। বরং, আমাদের গবেষণায় প্রাপ্ত উপাত্ত আর সাম্প্রতিকতম লিপিতাত্ত্বিক বিবরণীর ভিত্তিতে অনুমান করা যায় যে, সোমপুর মহাবিহারের আশেপাশে আরো স্থাপনা ও বসতি ছিল। এছাড়াও, সেন (২০১২) এর গবেষণার সঙ্গে সামঞ্জস্যপূর্ণ উপাত্তের ভিত্তিতে বলা যায় যে, একটি বা কয়েকটি মানব বসতি বৌদ্ধ মহাবিহারটিকে কেন্দ্র করে গড়ে উঠেছিল ৭ম-৮ম শতক ও তার পরবর্তী সময়ে। মহাবিহারটি কোনোভাবেই তৎকালীন সমাজ থেকে বিচ্ছিন্ন হয়ে লোকালয় থেকে দূরে গড়ে ওঠে নাই। প্রত্নতত্ত্ব অধিদপ্তর কর্তৃক পরিচালিত সাম্প্রতিক অনুসন্ধানমূলক খননের প্রকাশিত প্রতিবেদনে যে স্তরায়নের বর্ণনা আছে তা বিশ্লেষণ করে এবং সেই বিশ্লেষণের সঙ্গে দক্ষিণের খননের প্রতিবেদনসহ আরো কয়েকটি খননের প্রতিবেদনের (যেগুলোতে স্তরবিন্যাসের উল্লেখ নাই) তুলনামূলক আলোচনা করে এই প্রবন্ধে প্রথমবারের মতন বৌদ্ধ বিহারের কেন্দ্রীয় মন্দির ও সংলগ্ন বিহার-অঙ্গনের একটি শর্তসাপেক্ষ স্তরবিন্যাস প্রস্তাব করা হয়েছে। আপাতত নয়টি কালপর্বে বিভাজিত এই স্তরবিন্যাসের পর্যালোচনার মধ্য দিয়ে বেশকিছু অগ্রহোদ্বীপক তথ্য বের হয়ে এসেছে। ধর্মপাল নির্মিত এই মহাবিহারটির আগেও এখানে দুটি স্থাপত্যিক-কালপর্ব এবং একটি ইটের স্থাপত্যবিহীন বসতি-কালপর্বের অস্তিত্ব ছিল। বৌদ্ধ বিহার কেন্দ্রীক বসতিটির/ বসতিগুলোর ভূমিরূপগত প্রেক্ষিত সর্বশেষ গুরুত্বপূর্ণ। তিস্তা প্লাবন সমভূমির বালুযুক্ত পললের উপরে বিহার-পূর্ব পর্যায়ের স্থাপত্য-পূর্ববর্তী বসতির অস্তিত্ব রয়েছে। এ-ছাড়াও, কেন্দ্রীয় মন্দিরের পূর্ববর্তী আরেকটি স্থাপত্যপর্বের অস্তিত্বও পূর্ববর্তী প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিকগণ শনাক্ত করেছেন। দেখা যাচ্ছে, স্থাপত্য পূর্ববর্তী আদিমতম মানববসতিটি বন্যাবাহিত বালির নিচে চাপা পড়ে গিয়েছিল। প্রথম স্থাপত্য-পর্বের আলামতগুলোও বন্যাবাহিত বালির নিচে চাপা পড়া অবস্থায় পাওয়া গেছে। দ্বিতীয় স্থাপত্য কালপর্ব অর্থাৎ বর্তমান কেন্দ্রীয় মন্দির পূর্ববর্তী স্থাপনাটির উপরে বর্তমান মন্দির নির্মাণ করা হয়েছিল। আলোচ্য এই স্থাপনাটি নিয়ে পণ্ডিতদের মধ্যে তর্ক রয়েছে। কেউ কেউ এই স্থাপত্যটিতে পাহাড়পুরে প্রাপ্ত গুপ্তশাসক বৃষ্টিগুপ্তের সময়কালীন তাম্রপট্টে উল্লিখিত জৈন বিহার হিসাবে শনাক্ত করেছেন; আবার কেউ কেউ এটাকে একটি হিন্দু মন্দির হিসাবে প্রস্তাব করেছেন। কোনো কোনো পণ্ডিত এটাকে বৌদ্ধ মন্দির হিসাবেও চিহ্নিত করেছেন। দক্ষিণের খননের পরে যে খননগুলো পরিচালিত হয়েছে সেগুলোর প্রতিবেদনের সীমাবদ্ধতা এবং খননের স্থানিক সীমার স্বল্পতার ভিত্তিতে এই স্থাপনার প্রকৃতি বিচার করা দুর্ভাগ্য। তবে, বিভিন্ন তথ্য ও উপাত্ত বিশ্লেষণ করে বলা যেতে পারে যে, এই স্থাপনাটি কোনোভাবেই খ্রি. ৫ম শতকের অর্থাৎ গুপ্ত যুগের হতে পারে না। বর্তমানে উন্মোচিত স্থাপত্যকাঠামোগুলোও যে, বিভিন্ন কাঠামোগত পরিবর্তন ও পরিমার্জনের মধ্য দিয়ে গিয়েছে তা দক্ষিণ বলে গিয়েছেন। তবে সেই পরিবর্তনের স্তরবিন্যাসগত বিশ্লেষণ তিনি হাজির করেন নাই। ভূপ্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক গবেষণায় মহাবিহারকেন্দ্রীক মানববসতির মধ্যে ও চারপাশে অসংখ্য বিল, নিচুখাত ও আদি-নদীখাত পাওয়া গিয়েছে। প্লাবন সমভূমির তুলনামূলকভাবে অস্থিতিশীল প্রেক্ষিতে এবং নিয়ত গতিপথ পরিবর্তনশীল আঞ্চলিক নদীব্যবস্থার সাপেক্ষে এই বসতিটির/বসতিগুলোর রূপান্তর বোঝাও জরুরি বলে বিবেচনা করতে হবে বলে আমরা মনে করি। এমন একটি ভূমিরূপগত প্রেক্ষিতে বৌদ্ধবিহারসহ বসতি তৈরির কারণগুলো চিহ্নিত করতে হলে বৌদ্ধ বিহার ও বৌদ্ধ সঙ্ঘের প্রকৃতি ও কার্যপরিধি সম্পর্কে প্রচলিত ও প্রতিষ্ঠিত ধারণাকে আমাদের অতিক্রম করে যেতে

হবে। বৌদ্ধ বিহারগুলোকে কেবল জ্ঞান অর্জনের স্থান আর পার্থিব জীবন থেকে বিযুক্ত বৌদ্ধ শ্রমণদের ধর্ম-শাস্ত্র-সাধনার ও চর্চার পরিসর হিসাবে বুঝলে চলবে না। সাম্প্রতিককালে অনেক চিত্তকই দক্ষিণ এশিয়ায় বৌদ্ধ বিহারের ও বৌদ্ধ সঙ্ঘের ভূমিকা এবং কার্যপ্রণালির পরিধি ও বৈচিত্র্য নিয়ে আর সমাজের সঙ্গে তাদের বিভিন্নমাত্রিক জটিল সম্পর্ক নিয়ে নতুন নতুন অনুসন্ধান ও প্রসঙ্গ সামনে নিয়ে আসছেন। সেন (২০১২)-এর অনুসরণে আমরাও বলতে চাই যে, প্লাবনসমভূমিতে কৃষির সম্প্রসারণ ও ব্যবস্থাপনায় ইতোমধ্যে বিপুল পরিমাণ ভূসম্পত্তির মালিক হয়ে ওঠা বৌদ্ধবিহারগুলোর ভূমিকা প্রত্যক্ষ বা পরোক্ষভাবে তাৎপর্যপূর্ণ ছিল। সোমপুর মহাবিহারের বর্তমানে উন্মোচিত স্থাপত্য আর অন্যান্য স্থাপনার [যেমন, সম্প্রতি পাঠোদ্ধারকৃত ধর্মপালের সময়ের ইন্ডিয়ান মিউজিয়াম তাম্রপট্টে একজন সামন্তরাজা ভদ্রনাগ ও তার স্ত্রী কর্তৃক নির্মিত সোমপুর মহাবিহারে একটি বিহারের জন্য ভূমিদানের উল্লেখ আছে (ফুরুই ২০১১)] বৌদ্ধ সঙ্ঘগুলো কেবলমাত্র কৃষি ব্যবস্থাপনার সঙ্গে প্রত্যক্ষ বা পরোক্ষভাবে যুক্ত ছিল না। পাশাপাশি, স্তরবিন্যাস ও ভূমিরূপগতপ্রেক্ষিতের পর্যালোচনার ভিত্তিতে ধারণা করা যায় যে নিয়মিত বন্যার মোকাবেলা করা থেকে তারা বিযুক্ত থাকতে পারেনি। সোমপুর মহাবিহার কেন্দ্রীক বসতি, আর বৌদ্ধ সঙ্ঘ ও সাধারণ সমাজের মধ্যকার সম্পর্ক বিষয়ে এমন নতুন প্রস্তাবনাসমূহ উত্থাপন করার সাথে সাথে এই প্রবন্ধে অন্যান্য বেশ কিছু অনুমান আলামতের ভিত্তিতে করা হয়েছে। যেমন, ধর্মপালের ইন্ডিয়ান মিউজিয়াম তাম্রপট্টে দানকৃত ভূমির সীমানা হিসাবে চিরি ও প্রবর নামে দুটি নদীর উল্লেখ রয়েছে। উপগ্রহ আলোকচিত্র বিশ্লেষণ ও জরিপের মাধ্যমে চিহ্নিত করা বিভিন্ন আদি নদী খাতের বিন্যাস ও তাদের গতিপথ পরিবর্তনের দিক ও ধরন আর্কম্যাপ ১০- এ বিশ্লেষণ করে বর্তমান চিরি নদীকে ওই লিপিতে উল্লিখিত চিরিকা এবং বর্তমান ঘাঘর নদীর আদি খাতকে প্রবর নদী হিসাবে চিহ্নিত করা হয়েছে। পাশাপাশি, পঞ্চম দামোদরপুর তাম্রপট্টে উল্লিখিত যমু নদীকে আ ক ম যাকারিয়া বর্তমান ছোট যমুনা নদী হিসাবে শনাক্ত করেছেন। বর্তমান পাহাড়পুরের পশ্চিম দিক থেকে প্রবাহিত ছোট যমুনা নদীর আদি গতি পথকে এই যমু নদী হিসাবে চিহ্নিত করা হয়েছে। কৃষির উপযোগী সমতলভূমি দান যেমন বৌদ্ধ বিহার ও সঙ্ঘের কৃষি সম্পৃক্ততার প্রমাণ বহন করে, তেমনি ওই তাম্রপট্টের আলোকে অনুমান করা যায় যে, মহাসামন্ত ভদ্রনাগের শাসনের অন্তর্ভুক্ত এলাকার একটি অংশ, আর দানকৃত ভূমি তিস্তা প্লাবন সমভূমিতেই অবস্থিত ছিল। বর্তমান পাহাড়পুরের বিহার-অঙ্গনে আরো বিশদ, সুপরিকল্পিত ও স্তরবিন্যাসের বিশ্লেষণমুখী প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক খনন পরিচালনা করলে এবং পাহাড়পুরের পাশ্ববর্তী অঞ্চলে নিবিড় জরিপ পরিচালনা করলে প্রচলিত সঙ্কীর্ণ বৌদ্ধধর্মীয় প্রত্নতত্ত্বের সীমারেখা অতিক্রম করা ভবিষ্যতে সম্ভব হবে।

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Photographs

Plate 1: Central Temple of the monumental remains of Somapura Mahavihara

Plate 2: View of a wing of the mahavihara

Plate 3: View of the chaitya and the wing of the mahavihara

Plate 4: Potsherds from Goal Bhita

Plate 5: Collected bricks from Goal Bhita are being reused.

Plate 6: Heap of bricks and brick-fragments collected from Goal Bhita

Plate 7: The mound like high land in Goal Bhita

Plate 8: A section exposed in Goal Bhita

Plate 9: Paddy field on Occurrence 1

Plate 10: Brick-fragments collected from the brick-built remains (Occurrence 1)

Plate 11: Paddy field on Occurrence 2

Plate 12: Brick fragments collected from Occurrence 2

Plate 13: Paddy field on Occurrence 4

Plate 14: Brick fragments collected from Occurrence 4

Plate 15: Occurrence of potsherds in plough-zone (Occurrence 3)

Plate 16: Occurrence of potsherds in plough-zone (Occurrence 3)

Plate 17: Location of the trench (PAH. 2)

Plate 18: Section of PAH. 2

Plate 19: Location of the trench (PAH.1)

Plate 20: Location of the trench (PAH. 4) (Courtesy: Alam and Sultana 2013)

Plate 21: Dumped potsherds in the matrix of charcoal and ash

Plate 22: Close view of the dumped potsherds in the pit

Plate 23: Partial view of the west facing section in PAH.1 with deposits from various levels

Plate 24: Partial view of the west facing section in PAH.1

Plate 25: Close view of the matrix of brick-bats and potsherds in the deposit of Level III.

Plate 26: Depth of ring stands within the trench PAH.1

Plate 27: Ring stands within the flood-born sandy matrix

Plate 28: Ring stands from PAH.1 (Courtesy: Alam and Sultana 2013)

Plate 29: West facing section of PAH.2 (Courtesy: Alam and Sultana 2013)

Plate 30: Structure underneath the present central temple (Courtesy: Alam and Sultana 2013)

Plate 31: Partially exposed cell underneath the present central temple (Courtesy: Alam and Sultana 2013)

Plate 32: Parallel walls exposed in PAH.4 ((Courtesy: Alam and Sultana 2013)

Plate 33: Trench PAH.3 (view from the top) showing the section with the layer of charcoal on the earliest floor of the central temple [indicated by the black arrow] (Courtesy: Alam and Sultana 2013)

Plate 34: A stupa to the north of the entrance to the central temple on the Pradakhinapatha closing the passage in the later period (Courtesy: Alam and Sultana 2013)

Plate 35: A shrine built on the Pradakhinapatha in the later period of the central temple.

Plate 36: Partial view of Chhoto Jamuna River

Plate 37: Partial view of Chiri River

Plate 38: Partial view of Kata Jamuna River

Plate 39: Sandy outcrop outside the monumental remains showing cross-bedding

Plate 40: Sandy outcrop outside the monumental remains showing parallel bedding

Plate 41: Outcrop outside the monumental remains showing tabular cross bedding

Plate 42: Close view of the bedding structures

Plate 43: Structural remains in the courtyard of the mahavihara remains identified as the storage of crops.

Plate 44: Structural remains in the courtyard of the mahavihara remains identified as the storage of crops.

Plate 45: Structural remains in the courtyard of the mahavihara remains identified as the storage of crops.

Plate 46: Structural remains in the courtyard of the mahavihara remains identified as the storage of crops.

Plate 47: Present condition of Gandheshwari Temple.

Plate 48: Bronze Buddha statue with the marks of heating (Courtesy: DoA, GoB)